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Deliverable D4.2: How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations?
Evidence from five case studies.

A series of selected case studies to quantify different ways of incorporating the social perspective into an economic analysis to inform European decisions.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 779312. The results presented reflect the authors' views and not those of the European Commission.

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Executive summary

Economic evaluations are becoming of increasing importance to help policymakers to choose among many options when allocating scarce resources. One of the areas of greatest methodological discussion within the field of economic evaluations is the type of perspective to apply in such evaluations. Although some countries have decided to restrict economic evaluations to the perspective of the healthcare funder, others consider that not taking into account a wider perspective could mean excluding from the analysis costs and effects that are relevant to individual and societal well-being, thus causing bias in healthcare policies.

Thus, in this report, we aimed, first of all, to identify the presence of social costs (mainly productivity losses and informal care costs) in the economic evaluation of healthcare interventions in five therapeutic areas (Alzheimer's disease, Diabetes Mellitus, rare diseases, multiple sclerosis and depression). Secondly, to look in more detail at the impact that including social costs has on the results and conclusions of the economic evaluations performed, compared with the application of a healthcare funder's perspective. Finally, to conclude by summarizing the main findings identified in the report.

Throughout this document, we confirm that the inclusion of social costs in economic evaluations is quite rare, although major differences have been observed in different diseases. For example, the percentage of full economic evaluations that consider social costs (i.e. productivity losses and/or informal care costs) is 58% of the assessments identified through our search in the case of Alzheimer's disease, but barely 11% of the identified articles in the case of rare diseases-related interventions. Moreover, wide variations have also been found with respect to the changes in the results and conclusions of the economic evaluations. The consideration of social costs changed results of a 18%-30% of the economic evaluations, depending on the case study considered. However, the changes in conclusions were modest. More precisely, the conclusions changed in 4% of the economic evaluations in rare diseases, but almost 15% of the healthcare interventions related to multiple sclerosis modified their conclusions once productivity losses or informal care costs were considered.

The conclusions drawn from the analyses performed show that, although a recommendation for the application of a wider perspective (societal perspective) has been included in several international guidelines, the inclusion of social costs, mainly productivity losses and informal care costs, is limited in the existing literature. It should also be noted that their consideration did not significantly lead to changes in the results and conclusions of the majority of economic evaluations, although differences between diseases were found.

Context

A long, open and still unresolved debate is the perspective that should be considered in the economic evaluations of health interventions. Many evaluation agencies in different countries have chosen to consider the perspective of the health funder as principal in the base-case scenarios. Other agencies and institutions have pointed out that the social perspective should be the predominant one in economic evaluations. In any case, most of the guidelines of the agencies that have considered the perspective of the health funder admit that the use of a broader perspective (public funder or societal) as a complementary scenario could be included. Furthermore, when the societal perspective is recommended, it is also advisable to include separately the analysis derived from adopting the perspective of the health funder (see report Task 1).

The adoption of a social perspective involves a more complex analysis than with other perspectives, since it involves identifying, measuring and evaluating all costs and effects on health, not only from the point of view of the healthcare system, in the case of costs, and not only on patients, in the case of effects on health. In relation to costs, cost-of-illness studies have found that for many illnesses and injuries the economic impact in the non-healthcare sphere (informal care, productivity losses, to name the most frequent) can be more significant than the healthcare costs. With regard to effects on health, a disease can lead to significant changes in the quality of life and the health of caregivers, and, in the case of certain treatments such as vaccines, their effects can reach beyond the people who receive the treatments.

The objective of this report is not to adopt a position for or against a specific perspective, but to compare the practical consequences of adopting a social perspective with those resulting from the adoption of a health funder's perspective, in terms of the results obtained in economic evaluations, and, if significant differences are found, to consider whether this would affect the recommendations or decisions of agencies and funding institutions.

Given that the results, in terms of costs and effects on health, can be very different depending on the disease considered, we carried out this analysis by considering different cases. The selected diseases were chosen taking into account not only their prevalence and the strong impact on the state of health that such diseases cause, but also the fact that, in addition to the healthcare resources involved in their prevention and treatment, the social costs are very high. Thus the selected diseases were: Alzheimer's disease, Rare Diseases, Depression, Diabetes Mellitus and Multiple Sclerosis.

Methods

A systematic search of the literature was performed with the aim of identifying economic evaluations of any intervention in the selected diseases, taking into account the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) methodology.

In order to compare the results of the different studies and to analyze whether the changes in the results could lead to changes in the conclusions of the evaluations carried out and in the decisions of the public funders, we selected economic evaluations which measured outcomes in Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY). First, because this is the method most commonly used by health technology assessment agencies to measure health outcomes. Secondly, because discussions about the implementation of acceptability thresholds revolve around the opportunity cost of winning a QALY or, alternatively, around the social value given to a QALY^{1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8}.

In the case of **Alzheimer's Disease (AD)**, the search strategy was implemented in Medline (PubMed), using the following terms: ("Costs and Cost Analysis" OR "cost-effectiveness" OR "cost-utility" OR "cost-benefit" OR "economic evaluation" OR "economic analysis" OR "QALY" OR "quality-adjusted life years") AND ("Alzheimer Disease" OR "Alzheimer's disease" OR "dementia").

In the case of **Diabetes Mellitus (DM)**, the search strategy was implemented in PubMed (Medline) using the following key words: ("Costs and Cost Analysis" OR "cost-effectiveness" OR "cost-utility" OR "cost-benefit" OR "economic evaluation" OR "economic analysis" OR "QALY" OR "quality-adjusted life years") AND ("Diabetes" OR "diabetes mellitus"), where MeSH terms and natural key words in titles and abstracts were combined.

In the case of **Rare Diseases (RD)**, the search strategy included both formal terms (MeSH terms) and natural language, with the following economic terms: "Costs"; "Cost Analysis"; "cost-effectiveness"; "cost-utility"; "cost-benefit"; "economic evaluation"; "economic analysis"; "QALY"; "quality-adjusted life years". For the identification of rare-disease patients, we used the list of orphan drugs (ODs) listed on the website of the European Medicines Agency (EMA) on May 18 [<https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/download-medicine-data>] and we selected the 104

¹ Laupacis A, Feeny D, Detsky AS, Tugwell PX. How attractive does a new technology have to be to warrant adoption and utilization? Tentative guidelines for using clinical and economic evaluations. *CMAJ*. 1992 Feb 15;146(4):473-81

² Devlin N, Parkin D. Does NICE have a cost-effectiveness threshold and what other factors influence its decisions? A binary choice analysis. *Health Econ*. 2004 May;13(5):437-52

³ Bertram MY, Lauer JA, De Joncheere K, Edejer T, Hutubessy R, Kieny MP, Hill SR. Cost-effectiveness thresholds: pros and cons. *Bull World Health Organ*. 2016 Dec 1;94(12):925-930

⁴ Vallejo-Torres L, García-Lorenzo B, Castilla I, Valcárcel-Nazco C, García-Pérez L, Linertová R, Polentinos-Castro E, Serrano-Aguilar P. On the Estimation of the Cost-Effectiveness Threshold: Why, What, How? *Value Health*. 2016 Jul-Aug;19(5):558-66

⁵ Neumann PJ, Cohen JT, Weinstein MC. Updating cost-effectiveness--the curious resilience of the \$50,000-per-QALY threshold. *N Engl J Med*. 2014 Aug 28;371(9):796-7.

⁶ Claxton K, Martin S, Soares M, Rice N, Spackman E, Hinde S, Devlin N, Smith PC, Sculpher M. Methods for the estimation of the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence cost-effectiveness threshold. *Health Technol Assess*. 2015 Feb;19(14):1-503

⁷ Woods B, Revill P, Sculpher M, Claxton K. Country-level cost-effectiveness thresholds: initial estimates and the need for further research. *Value Health*. 2016;19(8):929-35

⁸ Cubi-Molla, P., Errea, M., Zhang, K. and Garau, M. Are Cost-Effectiveness Thresholds fit for Purpose for Real-World Decision Making? Consulting Report. Office of Health Economics, 2020; London. Accessed March 10, 2020.

active substances considered by the EMA as authorised orphan drugs. We then combined these substances with the above-mentioned economic terms in Medline.

In the case of **Multiple Sclerosis (MS)**, the search strategy was conducted in PubMed (Medline) using the following key words: Economic evaluation (including the terms: “Costs and Cost Analysis” OR “cost–effectiveness” OR “cost–utility” OR “cost–benefit” OR “economic evaluation” OR “economic analysis” OR “QALY” OR “quality-adjusted life years”) AND 2) Multiple sclerosis (including the terms: “multiple sclerosis” OR “sclerosis”).

In the case of **Depression**, the search strategy was conducted in PubMed (Medline) using the following key words: “cost-benefit analysis” OR “quality adjusted life year” OR “cost-benefit” OR “economic evaluation” OR “cost-effectiveness” OR “cost-utility” OR “economic analysis” AND “depression” OR “depress*”, where MeSH terms and natural key words in titles and abstracts were combined.

In order to improve the sensitivity of the strategy, we expanded the search in the **Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) Registry from TUFTS University**. The Registry uses an algorithm that is also deposited in Medline, but only includes studies that contained an original economic evaluation with a cost-utility analysis⁹.

All search strategies were limited to a period of ten years from January 2000 to 30 November 2018¹⁰. The studies’ eligibility criteria included: (i) original studies published in a scientific journal, (ii) economic evaluations of any intervention related to the disease, (iii) inclusion of social costs (informal care costs and/or productivity losses) in the analysis, (iv) publication in English, (v) using quality-adjusted life years (QALYs) as one of the outcomes for the analysis and (vi) provision separately of the results of the cost-effectiveness analysis according to the perspective applied. Studies were excluded if they were reviews of previous economic evaluations, methodological studies or were not full economic evaluations, such as cost-of-illness studies, burden of disease studies or budget impact analyses. Letters to the editor, editorials and congress communications were also excluded.

Data extraction

We collected the following data from the references that fulfilled the inclusion criteria: the first author, the year of publication, the type of analysis carried out (cost-utility or cost-effectiveness plus cost-utility), the country, the type of intervention assessed in the economic evaluation (e.g.

⁹ Center for the Evaluation of Value and Risk in Health. The Cost-Effectiveness Analysis Registry [Internet]. (Boston), Institute for Clinical Research and Health Policy Studies, Tufts Medical Center. Available from: www.cearegistry.org

¹⁰ When performing the case study of depression, the searching period was restricted to 30 November 2008 until 30 November 2018. In the case of multiple sclerosis, the searching period was from 1st January 2000 to 31st October 2019.

drugs, non-pharmaceutical therapy, diagnostic or screening device or a medical procedure), the perspective stated by the authors and the threshold assumed for the economic evaluation, the discount rates used for costs and outcomes, the time horizon, the type of sensitivity analysis performed, the costs included in the economic evaluation, and the Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios (ICURs) resulting from the new intervention compared with the alternative. Microsoft Excel was used to summarise the results from the systematic literature review.

Three researchers carried out the first screening, reviewing the title and abstract of the references, and the same three researchers performed the second review of full-text references. The discrepancies were resolved by another researcher.

With respect to the analysis of the effect that the inclusion of social costs might have, it is important to differentiate two different concepts. A change in conclusions is identified when, in cases where social costs are included, the conclusion about the adoption of a new technology is modified (i.e. from the healthcare payer's perspective, the ICUR is above the threshold value and, hence, the assessed technology will not be implemented as it is not cost-effective. However, when social costs are included, the ICUR is modified so that it lies below the corresponding threshold and the technology will be implemented). A change in results is reported when, although the conclusions do not change, when social costs are introduced, the intervention might become cost-saving, as the incremental costs might switch from positive from the healthcare perspective to negative from the societal perspective.

Definitions of costs

To identify and limit the concepts of healthcare and social costs, we followed the System of Health Accounts methodology proposed by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) in 2000 and revised in 2011¹¹. We included professional long-term care in healthcare costs. According to *A System of Health Accounts 2011*, revised edition, "Total long-term care consists of a range of medical/nursing care services, personal care services and assistance services that are consumed with the primary goal of alleviating pain and suffering or reducing or managing the deterioration in health status in patients with a degree of long-term dependency". Thus, the set of healthcare costs would encompass general practitioner (GP) and specialist visits, outpatient consultations, nursing care, pharmaceuticals, hospitalisations, imaging and laboratory tests, monitoring care, emergency visits, nursing home, community-based care, social services, out-of-pocket healthcare expenditure and the cost of travelling to be treated. Briefly, the loss of productivity was defined as the economic valuation of paid worktime lost by the patients as a result of the disease. Thus, when the direct healthcare costs plus the costs of social services were included, we called this the "healthcare payer's perspective", and when the estimate of loss of production

¹¹ OECD, Eurostat and World Health Organization (2017), *A System of Health Accounts 2011: Revised edition*, OECD Publishing, Paris.

and/or informal care cost was included in the cost analysis, we called this the “societal perspective”, as suggested in the international guides to the performance of economic evaluations in healthcare.

In principle, the application of the social perspective should involve considering effects on the health/well-being not only of the patients but also of other people in their environment (spillover effects) or even of people without a direct relationship with them (externalities). However, as we shall see, the consideration of these effects hardly appears in the studies. The application of the social perspective is restricted in most cases to the inclusion of non-health costs in the evaluations.

Main results

The main tables of results can be found in the report's appendices. To facilitate the identification of the selected articles and the results by disease, we made an appendix for each of them, showing the flowchart of the study identification and selection criteria, the characteristics of the studies selected, the main results from the economic evaluations reviewed and the references for each case study.

Case study 1. Alzheimer's disease (AD)

For Alzheimer's disease (**AD**), the search identified a total of 233 studies of interest. After reading all the manuscripts, we excluded 206 studies due to different exclusion criteria. We identified 81 full economic evaluations; 47 of them (58%) included social costs, but only 27 separated both perspectives (healthcare provider and societal). Hence, we selected 27 studies that were full economic evaluations, using QALYs as the main outcome, including social costs (productivity losses or informal caregiving costs or both of them) and with separated healthcare provider and societal perspectives. From the 27 selected studies, 55 interventions were found in which full economic evaluations were applied.

The results showed that only 6 out of these 55 economic evaluations (about 11%) changed their main conclusions when social costs were included. More precisely, in 3 of them, the new intervention became cost-effective when the societal perspective was considered, contrary to what occurred when using only the healthcare payer perspective. In other words, in these three economic evaluations whose conclusions changed, and in which, consequently, the new alternative switched to a cost-effective option, the factor that mainly explained this change was that informal caregiving costs were very different in the new intervention vs. its comparator. However, the remaining three economic evaluations showed the opposite pattern, leading to cost savings from the healthcare payer perspective but with increasing costs from the societal perspective.

Case study 2. Diabetes mellitus (DM)

For diabetes mellitus (**DM**), the search strategy implemented in PubMed retrieved 7,421 potential references to include in the review. In the CEA registry, we retrieved nearly 500 references. After eliminating the duplicates, we screened 7,857 records obtained from PubMed and the CEA registry. We found 738 economic evaluations of healthcare-related technologies and only 106 (14.36%) included social costs. However, in 31 of the manuscripts, either it was impossible to extract the ICURs from both cost perspectives, or the costs analysis was not reported separately. Finally, 28 studies did not include QALY as an outcome. Hence, 47 articles fulfilled all the inclusion criteria.

From the 47 studies included in the review it was possible to obtain 110 cost-utility analysis results. We observed changes in results or authors' conclusions after the inclusion of the societal costs in 20 economic evaluations (18.2%). Only four studies aimed to assess pharmaceutical interventions, the majority (n=8; 40% of the twenty ICUR estimates within changes in results or conclusions) being studies which assessed health education or behaviour programmes, followed by medical devices, which were assessed in four studies.

The economic evaluation conclusions changed in 8 economic evaluations. Informal care was included in only two studies and productivity losses in six studies. In six of these evaluations, healthcare interventions were more efficient than the comparator because the ICUR fell under the threshold recognised by the authors when including the societal costs. However, there were two other estimates in which the inclusion of social costs changed the conclusion in the opposite direction. The assessed interventions were cost-effective when the healthcare provider was applied, but not after the consideration of social costs. In another twelve estimates, changes in results were not translated into changes in the conclusions of the economic evaluations. In nine of them, the new intervention was already cost-effective (the ICUR was below the threshold) from the healthcare perspective, but it dominated the comparator when the societal costs were considered.

Case study 3. Rare diseases (RD)

For rare diseases (**RD**), after excluding duplicates and reviewing the titles and abstracts of the references retrieved from the search strategy, we evaluated the full text of 319 manuscripts, but finally, we identified 249 economic evaluation articles in patients with a rare disease from the year 2000 to November 2018. From the 319 full-text references reviewed, 52 did not finally apply a proper economic assessment design, one of them was a protocol and 15 were carried out in non-rare-disease patients. Only 11% (n=27) of the 249 economic evaluations included informal care costs or productivity losses in the assessment. Two studies were excluded from this review because QALYs were not included as an outcome in the assessment, and 36% of the remaining references (n=11) did not provide the incremental cost-utility ratio (ICUR) results separately, so it was not possible to extract the data from the results. Finally, we selected 14 articles that satisfied all the inclusion criteria.

When the societal perspective was considered, the results from one economic evaluation changed with respect to the results obtained from the healthcare payer's perspective. In this economic evaluation, the ICURs remained positive, but incorporating social costs into the economic evaluation made the assessed intervention cost-effective against the comparator. In another three estimates, the inclusion of social costs converted the ICUR from positive to negative, as the new intervention led to cost savings. However, the conclusions did not change, as the new intervention was already preferred to the comparator, from the healthcare payer's perspective. But from the societal perspective, the assessed intervention became not only cost-effective, but also a dominant strategy.

We found 8 estimates in which the ICURs from a societal perspective became even higher than from the healthcare payer's perspective, whereas 17 estimates were in the expected direction (ICURs lower than from the healthcare payer's perspective when a societal perspective was considered).

Case study 4. Multiple sclerosis (MS)

For multiple sclerosis (**MS**), 421 records were retrieved, after the elimination of duplicates, as Figure 1 shows. After reviewing titles and abstracts, 301 were excluded because they did not meet the study criteria, leaving 120 records for full-text review. From these, a further 91 were excluded for the following reasons: 22 were not full economic evaluations and 8 were not evaluations on multiple sclerosis (or if other diseases were included in the analysis, the results regarding MS could not be separated). Out of the 90 economic evaluations on multiple sclerosis, 42 of them did include social costs in their estimates (47%). However, from these, 11 did not separate perspectives (healthcare payer/provider from the societal perspective) and 2 papers did not use QALYs as an outcome. Hence, 29 studies met all the inclusion criteria and were finally included in the literature review.

67 economic evaluation analyses resulted from the 29 articles included. The inclusion of social costs (informal care costs and/or productivity losses) led to changes in the conclusions in 10 estimates. Three economic evaluations showed that, when informal care and productivity losses were included, the procedure that was the subject of analysis became cost-effective (as its cost per additional QALY was below the 30,000€ threshold stated by the authors), compared to its non-cost-effectiveness from the healthcare payer's perspective. Moreover, in another 3 evaluations, the inclusion of societal costs resulted in a more pronounced change: the assessed interventions became dominant from the societal perspective as they became cost-saving and led to greater gains in health, when, from the healthcare payer's perspective, they were not cost-effective. Conversely, in another 3 evaluations the assessed intervention was cost-effective when the analysis was performed from the healthcare payer's perspective, but it became dominated by the comparator when social costs were included, as it led to higher incremental costs and lower gains in health. Finally, in one evaluation the intervention was no longer as cost-effective when productivity losses were considered as it was from the healthcare payer/provider's perspective.

The inclusion of social costs also showed a change in results in 4 additional evaluations that were cost-effective from the healthcare payer/provider's perspective, but also dominant after the inclusion of social costs, because in addition to being better in terms of health outcomes, there were cost-savings.

Case study 5. Depression

For **Depression** 1,273 articles were identified by the initial search. After a review of all abstracts, 952 studies were excluded as duplicates or because they did not meet inclusion criteria. 321 publications remained for the full text screening, of which four were identified as duplicated or reduced versions of an included publication, seven followed a review design and 25 did not include a full economic evaluation or did not focus on depression (64 articles). From the remaining 221 articles which performed an economic evaluation of depression-related interventions, 92 considered social costs. However, 23 were excluded because they did not use QALYs (23 articles), and in 16 publications the perspectives of interest were not reported separately. So a total of 53 articles met the full inclusion criteria and were therefore included in this review.

The majority (70%) of the 53 economic evaluation studies included CEA as well as CUA. Considering the intervention type, 26% of the studies compared two or more different pharmaceuticals, whereas most of the articles evaluated non-pharmaceutical interventions such as cognitive behavioural therapy or other psycho-educational therapies. Collaborative care interventions were evaluated in 8 studies, and 7 articles focused on a combination of pharmaceutical and psychological interventions. Preventive approaches, screening, and diagnostic tools were used in 3 studies respectively.

In 20 of the publications more than one result was calculated, leading to a total of 92 economic evaluations for the 53 articles selected.

Regarding the differences in incremental costs, 19 economic evaluations from 14 studies calculated cost savings when societal costs were included. However, only 2 of these results led to a change of decision concerning the ICUR. The majority of the 16 studies that explicitly conducted an evaluation from both perspectives did not identify a substantial change in the cost-effectiveness of the focused intervention(s). Nevertheless, 20 single results out of these studies led to lower incremental costs by inclusion of societal costs. Irrespective of the perspective of the evaluation, 15 single estimates accounted for increasing incremental costs when the use of societal resources was included.

From the healthcare perspective, 10 out of 12 papers reported that the focused intervention dominated the comparator or had a positive ICUR below the threshold applied. When the societal costs were included, the majority of them showed no significant changes to the direct cost results. In two cases, the results changed from the intervention having a positive ICUR below the used threshold to being dominant. One study demonstrated a conclusion change for both single results from not being cost-effective when adopting the healthcare funder's perspective to being highly dominant when societal costs were included. However, another study changed from a positive ICUR to a value markedly above the chosen threshold of £30,000, when data from the healthcare funder's perspective were used.

In addition, when the societal perspective was selected, two results changed and became cost-effective compared to the analysis which only included direct costs. One of these studies ascertained

a complete change from a value far above the willingness-to-pay figure for one QALY to cost savings when societal costs were included, thus becoming not only cost-effective but also dominant. Another 8 economic estimates out of 6 studies changed from being below the threshold to dominating the standard care or other comparators. One of the interventions changed from being cost-effective to exceeding the threshold when societal costs were included. Further, one study changed in a similar ICUR but with negative incremental costs and negative incremental QALYs. In most of the single results from the societal perspective, no important changes in terms of cost-effectiveness were observed.

Comparison of diseases selected

A summary of the main results from the five case studies can be found in Table 1. As the table shows, there are pronounced differences between case studies with respect to the impact that the inclusion of social costs might have. From the articles that performed an economic evaluation in interventions related to Alzheimer's disease, 58% of them included social costs in their analyses (mainly explained by the role played by informal caregiving in this disease). This percentage is much lower for other diseases, such as rare diseases or Diabetes Mellitus, where it ranges between 10% and nearly 15% of the selected studies.

In cases in which results were changed, but not the conclusions of the economic evaluations,, the lowest rate of change was observed for multiple sclerosis (6%), whereas the rate reached almost 20% of the EE in the case of depression. Moreover, when looking at the effect on the conclusions, rare diseases showed the lowest percentage of changes in conclusions (3.85%) and multiple sclerosis showed the highest (almost 15%). However, the direction of those changes also differed between diseases, as shown by Table 1 and by a detailed description of the results of each condition studied.

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Table 1: Summary of the results derived from the five case studies about the selected diseases

Disease	Number of articles where the societal perspective was considered	Number of articles where societal and healthcare funder perspectives were considered independently	Number of EE that changed their results, but not their conclusions (and % of the total number of EE included)	Becomes cost-saving after including social costs	No longer cost-saving after including social costs	Number of EE where the change of results modified their conclusions (and % of the total number of EE included)	Becomes cost-effective (below the threshold) after including social costs	Becomes non-cost-effective (above the threshold) after including social costs
Alzheimer's disease	47 out of 81 (58.02%)	27 out of 47 (57.45%)	10 out of 55 (18.18%)	10	-	6 out of 55 (10.91%)	3	3
Diabetes Mellitus	106 out of 738 (14.36%)	47 out of 106 (44.34%)	12 out of 110 (10.91%)	9	3	8 out of 110 (7.27%)	6	2
Rare diseases	27 out of 249 (10.84%)	14 out of 27 (51.85%)	4 out of 26 (15.38%)	4	-	1 out of 26 (3.85%)	1	-
Multiple sclerosis	42 out of 90 (46.67%)	29 out of 42 (69.05%)	4 out of 67 (5.97%)	4	-	10 out of 67 (14.93%)	6	4
Depression	92 out of 221 (41.63%)	53 out of 92 (57.61%)	18 out of 92 (19.57%)	16	2	9 out of 92 (9.78%)	5	4

EE: Economic Evaluations

Note: A change in conclusions is identified when, in cases where social costs are included, the conclusion about the adoption of a new technology is modified (i.e. from the healthcare perspective, the ICUR is above the threshold value and, hence, the assessed technology will not be implemented as it is not cost-effective. However, when social costs are included, the ICUR is modified so that it lies below the corresponding threshold and the technology will be implemented).

Graphical analysis

Below are the graphical representations of the ICURs obtained from the economic evaluations reviewed for each case study. The top panel shows the results obtained when applying the perspective of the healthcare funder. The lower panel shows the results obtained when applying the societal perspective.

For ease of comparison, results are shown in additional euros per additional QALY. For this, the euro-currency exchange rates of the year of each article were applied. The values were not updated to any base year since the efficiency thresholds applied as a usual reference are usually kept constant over several years. In this sense, and to facilitate the interpretation of the results of both panels, two vectors were drawn with the values of € 30,000/QALY and € 50,000/QALY. These values were adopted as they are frequently cited thresholds in the economic evaluation literature¹².

In general, many of the results do not show significant variations between the ratios of the upper and lower panels. However, a general trend that can be observed in the figures of the five case studies considered is that some of the ICURs move towards the south, reaching the south-east quadrant and showing that some interventions with good cost-utility ratio, but positive, become dominant. We can also observe that in other cases, the step from the perspective of the healthcare funder involves a worsening of the ICUR.

The analysis of the figures for each disease offers results consistent with those already described and summarized in Table 1. The consideration of the social perspective instead of the health funder's perspective has more influence in the cases of Alzheimer's disease and depression. In both cases it is observed how some of the evaluations below the thresholds, but in the north-east quadrant, become cost-saving (south-east quadrant). This result, although less clearly, is also observed in the case of interventions in Diabetes Mellitus. In the case of multiple sclerosis, the most noticeable effect is that several interventions that had intermediate values between 30-50,000 €/QALY fall below the threshold of 30,000 €/QALY when the perspective of the healthcare funder is applied, or are even cost-saving when the social perspective is applied. Finally, the area where the smallest number of changes can be seen is that of rare diseases. In this sense, it should be noted that even though it has been considered higher value thresholds (80,000-100,000 €/QALY) additionally, the conclusions of the analyses for DR-related interventions would not modify

¹² Although in the literature reviewed it is recognized that the thresholds applied to interventions in rare diseases are usually higher than those indicated, for consistency with the rest of the figures it was decided to apply the same range of values of 30,000-50,000 €/ QALY. However, an additional threshold of 100,000€/QALY has been added in the case of rare diseases.

Figure 1. Alzheimer's Disease. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Figure 2. Diabetes Mellitus. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Figure 3. Rare Diseases. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Figure 4. Multiple Sclerosis Disease. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Figure 5. Depression. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Main conclusions and considerations

Several lessons can be drawn from the findings of the five case studies:

First, consideration of the societal perspective in the economic evaluations of health interventions published in scientific journals is less frequent than the consideration of the healthcare funder's perspective.

Second, the extent to which the societal perspective is considered differs sharply depending on the disease in question. Thus, the high societal costs of Alzheimer's disease seem to be reflected in the perspective adopted in the economic evaluations. On the other hand, in other diseases where there is also evidence of a high societal impact, such as in the case of rare diseases, the societal perspective is much less apparent.

Third, with diseases that have revealed high social costs (mainly the high costs of informal care or losses of productivity), the economic evaluations of technologies aimed at improving patients' health rarely take into account the effects on the patients' immediate surroundings. However, the consideration of the societal perspective should also include the changes in health outcomes beyond patients, such as those in the health of informal caregivers. This was very infrequent in the five case studies that we carried out; only the benefits to the patients were taken into account, with very few exceptions in cases of Alzheimer's Disease and depression.

Fourth, an analysis of the case studies shows that consideration of the societal perspective can result in substantial changes in a significant percentage of the results of the economic evaluations, although there is considerable heterogeneity depending on the therapeutic area considered. The inclusion of societal costs led to a change in results ranges from 18% to 30% of the economic evaluations, depending of the case study considered (including changes in results that did not imply change in conclusions and change in results that modified the conclusions of the evaluations).

Fifth, consideration of the societal perspective does not automatically result in a lower incremental cost-utility ratio value of the health technologies analysed. Several included studies revealed that consideration of the societal perspective made the ICUR higher. Although the reasons are diverse, a relevant one is that the use of the societal perspective reveals that certain interventions increase the burden of informal care, which is not reflected in the analyses that use the perspective of the healthcare funder.

Sixth, consideration of the societal perspective instead of the healthcare funder's perspective results in changes in a modest percentage of the conclusions of the studies analysed, varying from almost 4% in the case of rare diseases up to about 15% for multiple sclerosis. This is due to the fact that in several studies consideration of the societal perspective helps to identify social savings (lower labour losses, less non-health care needed) but in interventions whose incremental cost-utility ratios were already below the efficiency thresholds commonly used. In these cases, the conclusions of the analysis carried out from the perspective of the healthcare payer would be reinforced but not modified.

The above conclusions should be qualified by the following considerations. First, only a small percentage of the economic evaluations identified in the reviews could be used in the case studies. The main reasons were: (i) that most of them did not use the QALY as a measurement of the health outcome, which made it difficult to interpret the estimated ICERs, so it was decided to exclude them from the analysis; or (ii) the perspective used was exclusively the healthcare funder's; or (iii) even in those cases in which the perspective used was the societal one, in a significant number of cases the information contained in the articles did not make it possible to analyse the results of both perspectives separately.

Second, our case studies focused on original articles published in scientific journals. Consequently, reports from technology assessment agencies have not been reviewed, apart from those subsequently published in the aforementioned journals. However, in several of the most prolific agencies, in terms of publication of reports, as well as in the reports published by INAHTA/ EUNEHTA, the most used perspective is that of the healthcare funder. On the other hand, in most of the countries that recommend the use of the societal perspective, many of the economic evaluations are carried out directly by the pharmaceutical and health technology firms during the reimbursement and pricing process, while public agents, through evaluation agencies and expert committees, review the technical aspects of the evaluations presented. These reports are not public in most cases, so their use and identification through our search strategy was not possible. It is difficult to establish hypotheses about whether the inclusion of these studies would have modified or nuanced the conclusions of our review.

Third, assessing the technical quality of the economic evaluations reviewed would have exceeded the objective of our work. However, it is possible to point out several areas for improvement that would be easy to incorporate into the analyses. For instance, a fuller description of the methods used to assess the non-healthcare costs, the inclusion of unit costs used in the estimates and the explicit separation of results achieved by considering the perspective of the healthcare funder from those achieved with the societal perspective are still needed.

Although the objectives of the authors of the economic evaluations may be varied, the ultimate objective of this type of analysis is to provide useful information for decision-making. Due to the increasing burden of chronic conditions worldwide, this review of economic evaluations of healthcare interventions in five different diseases (Alzheimer's disease, rare diseases, depression, diabetes mellitus and multiple sclerosis) provides us with some figures which show how societal costs are included and their effect on the implementation of healthcare technologies. Improving the transparency of these simple elements would greatly improve comparability between studies and would favour the complementarity of the information provided by the economic evaluations carried out from both perspectives. Data and guidelines on the inclusion of societal costs for specific country settings are needed in order to provide us with estimates of the economic burden that some diseases impose on society.

Finally, it should be noted that this exercise can be transferred to other therapeutic areas to reveal to what extent the results of the five case studies are representative and can be extrapolated to all the economic evaluations of health technologies. This team is currently working on this and is looking forward to providing fruitful insights about the inclusion, valuation and effect of societal costs and outcomes in the economic evaluation field.

Dissemination of the results obtained

The results obtained from this report have been disseminated by different ways:

Manuscripts published in scientific journals

-Peña-Longobardo, L. M., Rodríguez-Sánchez, B., Oliva-Moreno, J., Aranda-Reneo, I., & López-Bastida, J. (2019). How relevant are social costs in economic evaluations? The case of Alzheimer's disease. *The European Journal of Health Economics*, 20(8), 1207-1236.

-Juliane Andrea Duevel, Lena Hasemann, Luz Maria Peña-Longobardo, Beatriz Rodríguez-Sánchez, Isaac Aranda-Reneo, Juan Oliva-Moreno, Julio López-Bastida, Wolfgang Greiner. (2020). Considering the societal perspective in economic evaluations: a systematic review in the case of depression. *Health Economics Review*. Accepted for publication

Manuscripts under review in scientific journals

-Aranda-Reneo I, Rodríguez-Sánchez, B., Peña-Longobardo LM, Oliva-Moreno, J., & López-Bastida, J. Can the consideration of social costs change the recommendation of economic evaluations in the field of rare diseases? An empirical analysis. Under review in *Value in Health*

Manuscripts in progress

- Rodríguez-Sánchez, B., Daugbjerg, S., Peña-Longobardo LM, Oliva-Moreno, Aranda-Reneo I., Cichetti, A., & López-Bastida, J. Social costs in multiple sclerosis economic evaluations: do their inclusion change the results and conclusions? A systematic review.

-Rodríguez-Sánchez, B., Oliva-Moreno, J., Aranda-Reneo I., Peña-Longobardo LM., & López-Bastida, J. Assessing the effect of including social costs in economic evaluations: A systematic review of diabetes-related interventions.

Works already or to be presented in international congresses

Peña-Longobardo, L. M., Rodríguez-Sánchez, B., Oliva-Moreno, J., Aranda-Reneo, I., & López-Bastida, J. How relevant are social costs in economic evaluations? The case of Alzheimer's disease. *JORNADAS DE ECONOMÍA DE LA SALUD*. Albacete. 2019

López-Bastida, J., Aranda-Reneo, I., Peña-Longobardo, L.M., Rodríguez-Sánchez, B., & Oliva-Moreno, J. How relevant are social costs in economic evaluations? The case of Rare Diseases. *ISPOR 2019*

López-Bastida, J., Rodríguez-Sánchez, B., Aranda-Reneo I., & Oliva-Moreno, J. Assessing the effect of including social costs in economic evaluations: A systematic review of diabetes-related interventions. *ISPOR 2020*

López-Bastida, J., Duevel, JA., Hasemann, L., Peña-Longobardo, LM., Rodríguez-Sánchez, B., Aranda-Reneo, I., Oliva-Moreno, J., & Greiner, W,. Considering the societal perspective in economic evaluations: a systematic review in the case of depression. ISPOR 2020

López-Bastida, J., Cichetti A, Rodríguez-Sánchez B, Daugberg S, Peña-Longobardo LM, Aranda-Reneo I, & Oliva-Moreno J. Social costs in multiple sclerosis economic evaluations: do their inclusion change the results and conclusions? A systematic review. ISPOR 2020

Appendix 1. ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

Figure 1: Flowchart of study identification and selection criteria

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Table 1: Characteristics of the 27 studies selected

Authors & publication year	Type of Economic Evaluation	Country	Intervention type	Perspective	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Currency (reference year)	Type of sensitivity analysis	Method used to calculate social costs
Michaud et al. (2018)	CUA	United States	Diagnostic / screening	Societal and healthcare payer [§]	3%; 3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> tests, medications, office visits for treatment, community-based care <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	United States Dollar (\$) / 2016	One-way deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analysis; Scenario analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> replacement cost method
Lamb et al. (2018)	CUA	United Kingdom	Non-pharmacological therapy	Healthcare payer and societal [§]	n.a.; n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> nursing and personal care, rehabilitation, hospital services, day care services, community care services, mental healthcare, social services, private health services <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2016	One-way deterministic sensitivity analysis; Scenario analysis	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method (paid time only)
Hornberger et al. (2017)	CUA	France	Diagnostic / screening	Societal and healthcare payer*	4%; 4%	10 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, imaging and laboratory tests, nursing home. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Euro (€) / 2016	One-way deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method (paid time only)
Tong et al. (2017)	CUA	United Kingdom	Diagnostic / screening	Societal and healthcare payer*	3.5%; 3.5%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> GP visits, practice nurse, laboratory tests, social care. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2016	One-way deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> n.a.
Knapp et al. (2017)	CUA	United Kingdom	Pharmaceutical	Healthcare payer and societal [§]	N/A; N/A	1 year	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> hospital care, medications, tests, community-based care. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2014	Societal perspective added	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost and replacement

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Type of Economic Evaluation	Country	Intervention type	Perspective	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Currency (reference year)	Type of sensitivity analysis	Method used to calculate social costs
										cost methods (unpaid time only)
Hornberger et al. (2015)	CUA	Spain	Diagnostic	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	10 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, diagnostic tests, nursing home. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Euro (€) / 2010	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
Saint-Laurent et al. (2015)	CUA	United States	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer*	3%; 3%	3 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, monitoring, medical care. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	United States Dollar (\$) / 2013	One-way deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> n.a.
D'Amico et al. (2015)	CUA/CEA	United Kingdom	Medical procedure	Healthcare payer and societal [§]	3.5%; 3.5%	6 months	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> hospital and day services, equipment and adaptation, medications, social and community care. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2011	One-way deterministic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method (unpaid time only)
Orgeta et al. (2015)	CUA	United Kingdom	Non-pharmacological therapy	Societal and healthcare payer	n.a.; n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> nursing and home care, hospital care (inpatient, day, outpatient and accident and emergency services), primary and community health and social care, out of pocket payments (travel expenses to healthcare and social care appointments) <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2012	One-way deterministic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost and replacement cost methods (unpaid time only)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Type of Economic Evaluation	Country	Intervention type	Perspective	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Currency (reference year)	Type of sensitivity analysis	Method used to calculate social costs
Touchon et al. (2014)	CUA	France	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	7 years	Healthcare cost: medications, hospitalizations, medical visits, emergency visits, other medical costs, nursing home care. Social costs: informal care	Euro (€) / 2013	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs</u> : n.a.
Sogaard et al. (2014)	CUA	Denmark	Non-pharmacological therapy	Societal and healthcare payer ^s	3%; 3%	3 years	Healthcare cost: hospitalizations, primary care visits, nursing home care. Social costs: informal care and productivity losses	Euro (€) / 2008	One-way deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs</u> : opportunity cost method (paid and unpaid time)
Romeo et al. (2013)	CUA/CEA	United Kingdom	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	N/A; N/A	9 months	Healthcare cost: hospitalizations, primary care visits, social services. Social costs: informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2010	One-way deterministic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs</u> : opportunity cost and replacement cost methods (unpaid time only)
Pfeil et al. (2012)	CUA	Switzerland	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	8 years	Healthcare cost: medications, hospitalizations, medical visits, nursing home care. Social costs: informal care	Euro (€) / 2010	One-way deterministic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs</u> : n.a.
Hartz et al. (2012)	CUA	Germany	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	10 years	Healthcare cost: medication; hospitalizations; medical visits, other medical costs, and social services. Social costs: informal care	Euro (€) / 2008	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs</u> : opportunity cost method (unpaid time only)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Type of Economic Evaluation	Country	Intervention type	Perspective	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Currency (reference year)	Type of sensitivity analysis	Method used to calculate social costs
Rive et al. (2012)	CUA	Norway	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	5 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, hospitalizations, medical visits, emergency visits, and social services. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Norwegian Kroner & Euro (€) / 2009	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
Getsios et al. (2012)	CUA	United Kingdom	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3.5%; 3.5%	10 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> visits to GPs and medical doctors, medications, tests, nursing home care. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2007	One-way deterministic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method (unpaid time only)
Guo et al. (2012)	CUA	United States	Diagnostic / screening	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, medical care, social services. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	United States Dollar (\$) / 2011	One-way deterministic and probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
Woods et al. (2012)	CUA/CEA	United Kingdom	Non-pharmacological therapy	Societal and healthcare payer*	n.a.; n.a.	10 months	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> nursing care, GP, health visitor, community psychiatrist, psychologist, counsellor, physiotherapist, occupational therapist, care manager, social worker, home-care worker, care attendant, family support worker, dietician. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2010	Scenario analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> n.a.
Lachaine et al. (2011)	CUA	Canada	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	5%; 5%	7 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, other medical costs, social services. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Canadian Dollar (\$) / 2010	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method (paid and unpaid time)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Type of Economic Evaluation	Country	Intervention type	Perspective	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Currency (reference year)	Type of sensitivity analysis	Method used to calculate social costs
									sensitivity analysis	
Nagy et al. (2011)	CUA	United Kingdom	Pharmaceutical	Healthcare payer and societal [§]	3.5%; 3.5%	5 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, outpatient visit costs, nursing home care, standard community care. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2008	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method (unpaid time only)
Getsios et al. (2010)	CUA	United Kingdom	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3.5%; 3.5%	5 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, other medical care and social care. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Pound Sterling (£) / 2007	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method (unpaid time only)
López-Bastida et al. (2009)	CUA	Spain	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	30 months	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, hospitalizations, medical visits, emergency visits. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Euro (€) / 2006	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
Wolfs et al. (2009)	CUA	The Netherlands	Diagnostic	Societal and healthcare payer*	N/A; N/A	1 year	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> hospital care, medications, nursing home care, home care, out-of-pocket expenditures, travelling costs. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	Euro (€) / 2005	One-way deterministic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
Fuh et al. (2008)	CUA	Taiwan	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	6 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> medications, other medical care. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	United States Dollar (\$) / 2006	One-way and multivariate deterministic; probabilistic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost and replacement cost methods (paid time only)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Type of Economic Evaluation	Country	Intervention type	Perspective	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Currency (reference year)	Type of sensitivity analysis	Method used to calculate social costs
Kirbach et al. (2008)	CUA	United States	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer	3%; 3%	13 years	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : physician visits, medications; outpatient and inpatient hospital care. <u>Social costs</u> : informal care	United States Dollar (\$) / 2006	Multivariate deterministic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs</u> : n.a.
Weycker et al. (2007)	CUA	United States	Pharmaceutical	Societal and healthcare payer*	3%; 3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : medications, hospitalizations, social services. <u>Social costs</u> : informal care	United States Dollar (\$) / 2005	Multivariate deterministic sensitivity analysis	<u>Informal care costs</u> : replacement cost method
McMahon et al. (2000)	CUA	United States	Diagnostic / screening	Societal and healthcare payer [§]	3%; 3%	18 months	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : drug costs and two follow-up visits, laboratory and diagnostic tests. <u>Social costs</u> : informal care	United States Dollar (\$) / 1998	One-way deterministic sensitivity analysis; Scenario analysis	<u>Informal care costs</u> : opportunity cost method

CUA: Cost-Utility Analysis; CEA: Cost-Effectiveness Analysis; GP: General Practitioner; N/A: Not available

* The perspective of the analysis could be extracted from tables or the main text. [§] The perspective of the analysis could be extracted from the sensitivity analysis.

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Table 2: Results from full economic evaluations of Alzheimer's disease

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
1	Michaud et al. (2018)	354	0.004	88,500	142	0.004	35,500	NO	NO	\$100,000
2	Michaud et al. (2018)	1,137	0.038	29,921	490	0.038	12,895	NO	NO	\$100,000
3	Michaud et al. (2018)	1,953	0.156	12,519	4,709	0.156	30,186	NO	NO	\$100,000
4	Michaud et al. (2018)	3,373	0.176	19,165	5,693	0.176	32,347	NO	NO	\$100,000
5	Michaud et al. (2018)	3,726	0.18	20,700	5,835	0.18	32,417	NO	NO	\$100,000
6	Lamb et al. ¹³ (2018)	1,347	-0.039	-34,538	1,301	-0.063	-20,651	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
7	Hornberger et al. (2017)	909	0.021	43,286	470	0.021	21,888	YES	NO	€40,000
8	Hornberger et al. (2017)	947	0.022	43,045	528	0.022	24,084	YES	NO	€40,000
9	Tong et al. (2017)	-65,755	0.1031	-637,779	-66,566	0.1031	-645,645	NO	NO	£30,000
10	Tong et al. (2017)	693	3.4847	199	-7,845	3.4847	-2,251	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£30,000
11	Tong et al. (2017)	-185,846	0.3063	-606,745	-187,064	0.3063	-610,722	NO	NO	£30,000

¹³ Differences in effects on health when including social costs are due to the inclusion of caregiver's utility values.

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
12	Knapp et al. ¹⁴ Marcador n o definido. (2017)	-389	0.11	-3,536	-2669	0.09	-29,656	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
13	Knapp et al. ¹⁴ (2017)	-1,409	0.07	-20,129	-1,457	0.02	-72,850	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
14	Knapp et al. ¹⁴ Marcador n o definido. (2017)	599	0.03	19,967	-331	0.01	-33,100	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£20,000-30,000
15	Hornberger et al. (2015)	601	0.008	76,268	36	0.008	4,769	YES	NO	€30,000
16	Saint-Laurent et al. (2015)	-20,947	0.13	-161,131	-18,355	0.13	-152,958	NO	NO	\$50,000
17	D'Amico et al. (2015)	475	0.0013	365,276	1,146	0.0013	882,801	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
18	D'Amico et al. (2015)	474	0.0176	26,835	1,143	0.0176	64,842	YES	NO	£20,000-30,000
19	D'Amico et al. (2015)	518	0.0039	132,539	1,575	0.0039	400,993	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
20	D'Amico et al. (2015)	402	0.0062	64,785	1,259	0.0062	205,079	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
21	Orgeta et al. (2015)	140	0.05	2,800	-1,710	0.05	-34,200	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving	£20,000-30,000

¹⁴ Differences in effects change when social costs are included due to the smaller sample with a societal perspective.

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
									and, hence, dominates the comparator	
22	Orgeta et al. (2015)	140	0.05	2,800	-3,510	0.05	-70,200	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£20,000-30,000
23	Touchon et al. (2014)	-8,341	0.25	-33,364	-3,318	0.25	-13,272	NO	NO	€23,000-35,000
24	Sogaard et al. ¹³ (2014)	-957	-0.17	5,629	15,348	-0.38	-40,390	YES	NO	€100,000
25	Sogaard et al. ¹³ (2014)	-4,433	-0.06	73,883	3,401	-0.09	-37,789	YES	NO	€100,000
26	Romeo et al. (2013)	693	0.03	23,100	705	0.03	23,500	NO	NO	£30,000
27	Romeo et al. (2013)	404	0.05	8080	-1,106	0.05	-22,120	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£30,000
28	Romeo et al. (2013)	-289	0.02	-14,450	-1,811	0.02	-90,550	NO	NO	£30,000
29	Romeo et al. (2013)	-23,312	0.12	-194,263	-4,029	0.12	-33,576	NO	NO	£30,000
30	Pfeil et al. (2012)	-27,656	0.12	-230,467	-4,780	0.12	-39,833	NO	NO	CHF 100,000
31	Hartz et al. (2012)	-7,007	0.146	-47,993	-9,893	0.146	-67,760	NO	NO	N.A.

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
32	Hartz et al. (2012)	-1,960	0.017	-115,294	-2,825	0.017	-166,176	NO	NO	N.A.
33	Rive et al. (2012)	-47,186	0.03	-1,572,867	-30,041	0.03	-1,001,367	NO	NO	N.A.
34	Getsios et al. (2012)	-3,593	0.17	-21,135	-7,741	0.17	-45,535	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
35	Getsios et al. (2012)	-2,135	0.13	-16,423	-5,726	0.13	-44,046	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
36	Guo et al. ^{Error! Marcador no definido.} (2012)	-12,374	0.15	-82,493	-11,086	0.03	-369,533	NO	NO	\$ 50,000
37	Guo et al. ^{Error! Marcador no definido.} (2012)	-11,806	0.15	-78,707	-11,389	0.03	-379,633	NO	NO	\$ 50,000
38	Woods et al. (2012)	1,544	0.001	1,544,000	2,680	0.001	2,680,000	NO	NO	N.A.
39	Lachaine et al. (2011)	-30,512	0.26	-117,354	-21,391	0.26	-82,273	NO	NO	N.A.
40	Nagy et al. (2011)	1,174	0.1109	10,579	-570	0.1109	5,135	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£20,000
41	Nagy et al. (2011)	1,011	0.1109	9,114	301	0.1109	2,716	NO	NO	£20,000
42	Getsios et al. (2010)	-2,337	0.12	-19,475	-4,769	0.12	-39,742	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
43	López-Bastida et al. (2009)	1,971	0.097	20,353	-1,273	0.097	-13,124	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced,	€25,000-30,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
									the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	
44	López-Bastida et al. (2009)	2,043	0.029	70,448	1,080	0.029	37,241	NO	NO	€25,000-30,000
45	Wolfs et al. (2009)	316	0.05	6,320	65	0.05	1,267	NO	NO	€45,000
46	Fuh et al. (2008)	3,677	0.525	7,009	-8,153	0.525	-15,529	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	\$15,000-20,000
47	Kirbach et al. (2008)	5,566	0.15	37,104	1,985	0.15	13,230	NO	NO	\$50,000
48	Weycker et al. (2007)	334	0.0126	26,508	44	0.0126	3,475	NO	NO	\$50,000
49	Weycker et al. (2007)	521	0.0275	18,946	10	0.0275	382	NO	NO	\$50,000
50	Weycker et al. (2007)	221	0.0275	8,036	-140	0.0275	-5,102	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	\$50,000
51	Weycker et al. (2007)	150	0.0276	5,436	-182	0.0276	-6,613	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving	\$50,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
									and, hence, dominates the comparator	
52	Weycker et al. (2007)	-62	0.0272	-2,279	-242	0.0272	-8,897	NO	NO	\$50,000
53	McMahon et al. (2000)	N.A.	-0.0038	Dominated	600	-0.0038	-157,895	NO	NO	N.A.
54	McMahon et al. (2000)	N.A.	-0.0001	Dominated	787	-0.0001	-7,870,000	NO	NO	N.A.
55	McMahon et al. (2000)	691	0.0021	328,830	1,007	0.0021	479,524	NO	NO	N.A.

A change in conclusions is identified when, in cases where social costs are included, the conclusion about the adoption of a new technology is modified (i.e. from the healthcare payer's perspective, the ICUR is above the threshold value and, hence, the assessed technology will not be implemented as it is not cost-effective. However, when social costs are included, the ICUR is modified so that it lies below the corresponding threshold and the technology will be implemented). A change in results is reported when, although the conclusions do not change, when social costs are introduced, the intervention might become cost-saving, as the incremental costs might switch from positive from the healthcare perspective to negative from the societal perspective.

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Appendix 2. DIABETES MELLITUS

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart of the search strategy

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Table 1. Descriptive information about the selected studies (n = 47)

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Broekhuizen et al. (2018)	Gestational diabetes mellitus	Health education or behaviour	United Kingdom, Ireland, Austria, Poland, Italy, Spain, Denmark, Belgium, and the Netherlands (2012€)	n.a./n.a.	48 weeks	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : primary and secondary healthcare, medication, travel costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
De Wit et al. (2018)	Diabetes mellitus type 1 or type 2	Health education or behaviour	The Netherlands (2015€)	n.a./n.a.	6 months	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : hospital admissions, outpatient visits and calls, emergency room visits, ambulance transfers, medication and use of medical supplies <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses</u> : friction cost method (paid (absenteeism and presenteeism) and unpaid work) <u>Informal care</u> : n.a.
Ericsson et al. (2018)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2015SEKs)	3%;3%	40 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : anti-hyperglycaemic treatment and other treatment costs, diabetes-related complications <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Breeze et al. (2017)	Diabetes	Health education or behaviour	UK (2014/15£)	1.5%, 1.5%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : direct healthcare costs, intervention and HbA1c testing costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : friction cost approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Jendel et al. (2017)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Medical device / pharmaceutical	Sweden (2015SEKs)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : intervention costs (insulin sensor), self-monitoring of blood glucose strips, diabetes-related complications <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Landstedt.Hallin et al. (2017)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Medical device / pharmaceutical	Sweden (2015SEKs)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : direct healthcare costs financed by tax payments and co-payments <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Roze et al. (2017)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Medical device	Denmark (2015DKK)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : direct medical costs due to diabetes-related complications, intervention costs (blood glucose self-testing) <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Slangen et al. (2017)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Surgical	Netherlands (2012€)	4%; 1.5%	12 months	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : specialist doctor, surgery, laboratory tests, reviews, paramedical visits, follow-up visits, medication, inpatient admission costs	<u>Productivity losses</u> : friction cost method (paid time (absenteeism))

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						<u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care costs	<u>Informal care</u> : opportunity cost method
Farshchi et al. (2016)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical	Iran (2012US\$)	n.a/n.a.	48 weeks	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : laboratory, medications, clinician visits, inpatient, non-medical costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : n.a.
Haig et al. (2016)	Diabetes mellitus type 1 or type 2	Medical procedure, pharmaceutical	Canada (2013CAN\$)	5%; 5%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : treatment and monitoring visits, complications, treatment costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care costs	<u>Productivity losses</u> : n.a. <u>Informal care</u> : n.a.
Kolu et al. (2016)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Health education intervention	Finland (2015€)	Not specified	7 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : primary care doctor, specialist doctor, nursing, physiotherapist, medication, inpatient admission costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care costs	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism costs)) <u>Informal care</u> : opportunity cost method (paid time)
Lian et al. (2016)	Diabetes	Screening	China (2009HK\$)	3.5%; 3.5%	n.a.	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : staff time costs, co-payment intervention cost, capital costs, follow-up and treatment costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Nguyen et al. (2016)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Screening	Singapore (2015 Singapore\$)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : screening, follow-up visits, laser treatment, transport costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Roussel et al. (2016)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical	France (2013€)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : diabetes medications, self-monitoring of blood glucose, concomitant medications and diabetes-related complications costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : n.a. (paid time (absenteeism))
Roze et al. (2016)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Medical device, pharmaceutical	United Kingdom (2013£)	3.5%; 1.5%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : treatment costs (strips, lancets, transmitter and glucose sensors) and diabetes-related complication costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Roze et al. (2016)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Medical device, pharmaceutical	France (2014€)	4%; 4%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : treatment costs (strips, lancets, transmitter and glucose sensors) and diabetes-related complication costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Roze et al. (2016)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Pharmaceutical	Netherlands (2013€)	4%; 1.5%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : treatment costs (strips, lancets, transmitter and glucose sensors) and diabetes-related complication costs	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						<u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	
Brown et al. (2015)	Diabetes mellitus type 1 or type 2	Pharmaceutical	US (2012US\$)	3%;3%	14 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : disease management and treatment costs, complications and adverse events costs, insurer costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care costs	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time)
Cutino et al. (2015)	Diabetes mellitus type 1 or type 2	Medical device	US (2014US\$)	Not specified	15 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : drug study costs, administration and monitoring costs, concomitant treatments, adverse events <u>Social costs</u> : informal care costs	<u>Informal care</u> : opportunity costs (paid time)
Huetson et al. (2015)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical	Norway (2012NOKs)	4%; 4%	45 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : disease management and treatment costs, complications costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time)
Roze et al. (2015)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Medical device	Sweden (2011SEKs)	3%; 3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : intervention costs and diabetes-related complications costs (cardiovascular, renal, acute events, eye disease and other) <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Kiadaliri et al. (2014)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2014SEKs)	n.a/n.a.	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : drugs, self-monitoring blood glucose test strips and lancets, diabetes-related complications costs, costs due to treatment side effects <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach
Png et al. (2014)	Diabetes mellitus type 2 and prediabetes	Health education or behaviour - Pharmaceutical	Singapore (2012US\$)	3%; 3%	3 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : outpatient care, laboratory tests and medications <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Steen-Carlsson & Persson (2014)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2013SEKs)	n.a/n.a.	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : preventive treatment, micro- and macrovascular complications costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach
Tsiachristas et al. (2014)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Management programme intervention	Netherlands (2012€)	n.a/n.a.	12 months	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : GP, nursing practitioner, nurse, dietician, physiotherapist, podiatrist, lifestyle coach, medical specialists in outpatient clinics, etc., hospital admissions and admission days, and medication use <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : friction cost method (paid time (absenteeism))

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Ericsson et al. (2013)	Diabetes mellitus type 1 or type 2	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2012 SEKs)	n.a/n.a.	1 year	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> insulin costs, needles, self-monitoring blood glucose test strips and lancets, visits to general practitioner (GP) , GP home visit, and emergency department visit</p> <p><u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))</p>
Saha et al. (2013)	Diabetes	Physical exercise plus nutritional recommendations	Sweden (2012US\$)	3%;3%	85 years	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> medical treatment costs, costs for institutional healthcare, pharmaceuticals</p> <p><u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care costs</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (paid time due to morbidity)</p> <p><u>Informal care:</u> opportunity cost method (non-paid time) and replacement cost method</p>
De Salas-Cansado et al. (2012)	Diabetes	Pharmaceutical	Spain (2006€)	n.a/n.a.	12 weeks	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> drug and non-drug treatments, medical visits, hospitalizations and diagnostic tests</p> <p><u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism and presenteeism))</p>
Kamble et al. (2012)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Medical device	United States (2010US\$)	3%; 3%	60 years	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> costs of glucose meters and test strips, lancets, insulin, and provider's time to obtain annual treatment costs, costs of insulin pumps, transmitters, sensors,</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))</p>

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						insertion devices and other pump supplies <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	
Oostdam et al. (2012)	gestational diabetes	Non-pharmaceutical (exercise intervention)	Netherlands (2009€)	n.a/n.a.	32 weeks	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : visits to healthcare providers, medication <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care costs	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism)) and friction cost method (paid time (absenteeism)) <u>Informal care</u> : n.a.
Smith-Palmer et al. (2012)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2010SEKs)	3%;3%	Lifetime (40 years)	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : diabetes-related complications costs, medications, self-monitoring blood glucose tests costs, treatment costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach
Greeley et al. (2011)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Screening	United States (2008US\$)	3%;3%	10, 20 and 30 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : medications, test strips, complications costs <u>Social costs</u> : informal care costs	<u>Informal care</u> : n.a. (paid time)
Kasteng et al. (2011)	Diabetes mellitus type 1 or type 2	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2009SEKs)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : intervention drug costs, complications costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Kuo et al. (2011)	Diabetes mellitus type 1 or type 2	Care delivery	United States (2010US\$)	3%;3%	20 years	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: endocrinologist, registered/certified nurse or diabetes educator, exercise physiologist, medical assistant, rotated staff, laboratory tests, physician's office hours, complications costs</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: human capital approach (paid time)</p>
Patel et al. (2011)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Health education or behaviour	United Kingdom (2006£)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: hospital inpatient and outpatient services, primary care services, other community-based services, social services, medications, insulin-related equipment, other equipment and adaptations and intervention costs</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses and informal care costs</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: n.a. (paid time (absenteeism and presenteeism) and non-paid time)</p> <p><u>Informal care</u>: n.a.</p>
Valentine et al. (2011)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical	Switzerland (2008€)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: medications and treatment costs, complications costs</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))</p>
Valentine et al. (2011)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2006SEKs)	3%;3%	50 years	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: diabetes-related complications costs, pharmacy costs</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))</p>

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Huang et al. (2010)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Diagnostic - Medical device	United States (2008US\$)	n.a/n.a.	Lifetime	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: intervention's technology and treatment costs, standard glucose monitoring costs, routine office visits, after-hours clinic visits, emergency room visits, 911 calls, and hospitalizations</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses and informal care costs</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism and presenteeism))</p> <p><u>Informal care</u>: opportunity cost method (paid time)</p>
Ismail et al. (2010)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Non-pharmacological intervention	United Kingdom (2005/06£)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: hospital inpatient and outpatient services, primary care services, other community-based services, social services, medications, insulin-related equipment, other equipment and adaptations and the cost of the interventions</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses and informal care costs</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: human capital approach (paid and non-paid time)</p> <p><u>Informal care</u>: opportunity cost method (paid and non-paid time)</p>
Gschwend et al. (2009)	Diabetes mellitus type 1	Pharmaceutical	Belgium, France, Germany, Italy and Spain (2006€)	Belgium 3% costs, 1.5% benefits; France 3% both; Germany 5% both; Italy 3%	Lifetime	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: diabetes-related complication costs, medication (insulin) and needles and devices for self-monitoring of blood glucose</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: human capital approach</p>

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Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
				both; Spain 6% both			
Lindgren et al. (2007)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Health education or behaviour	Sweden (2003€)	3%;3%	n.a.	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : intervention costs, physician visits, nutritionist visits, training sessions, travel time, diabetes-related complications costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Valentine et al. (2006)	Diabetes	Pharmaceutical	United States (2002US\$)	3%;3%	35 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : treatment, diabetes-related complications, medication costs <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Eddy et al. (2005)	Diabetes	Health education or behaviour	United States (2000US\$)	3%;3%	30 years	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : hospital admissions and emergency department visits, office and clinic visits, tests and discrete procedures, medications and ongoing programmes <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism and presenteeism))
Herman et al. (2005)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Health education intervention - Pharmaceutical	United States (2000US\$)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : intervention costs, diabetes-related complication costs, physician visits, hospitalizations <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : n.a.

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Authors & publication year	Diabetes type	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Rosen et al. (2005)	Diabetes	Pharmaceutical	United States (2003US\$)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: intervention costs, diabetes-related complication costs, ongoing costs of care, medication costs</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses and informal care costs</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: n.a.</p> <p><u>Informal care</u>: n.a.</p>
The Diabetes Prevention Program Research Group (2003)	Diabetes mellitus type 2	Pharmaceutical - Health education or behaviour	United States (2000US\$)	3%;3%	3 years	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: intervention costs, side effects of the intervention, care outside the prevention programme (hospital, emergency room, urgent care, and outpatient services; telephone calls to healthcare providers; and prescription medications), travel costs</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))</p>
Almbrand et al. (2000)	Diabetes mellitus type 1 or type 2	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (1999€)	3%;3%	Lifetime	<p><u>Healthcare costs</u>: medication costs, hospitalizations, post-hospital discharge costs, diagnostic and monitoring procedures and tests, and outpatient visits</p> <p><u>Social costs</u>: productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses</u>: human capital approach (paid time)</p>

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Table 2. Incremental costs, QALYs and ICURs from the healthcare payer/provider's perspective and the societal perspective

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		Δ Costs	Δ QALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Δ Costs	Δ QALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
1	Broekhuizen et al (2018)	-1,057	0.02	-52,850	-1,627	0.02	-91,254	NO	NO	€10,000-24,400
2	Broekhuizen et al (2018)	-23	-0.003	7,667	653	-0.003	-241,959	YES	NO	€10,000-24,400
3	Broekhuizen et al (2018)	-446	-0.008	55,750	-1,155	-0.008	146,179	NO	NO	€10,000-24,400
4	de Wit et al. (2018)	-197	-0.0008	247,388	708	-0.0008	-888,936	NO	YES, when social costs are included, the intervention is no longer cost-saving	€20,000
5	de Wit et al. (2018)	-197	-0.001	23,130	708	-0.001	-83,112	NO	YES, when social costs are included, the intervention is no longer cost-saving	€20,000
6	Ericsson et al (2018)	28,028	0.86	32,591	26,414	0.86	30,714	NO	NO	SEKs 100,000-500,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
7	Breeze et al (2017)	-4.8	0.0003	-16,000	-4.92	0.0003	-16,400	NO	NO	£20,000
8	Breeze et al (2017)	-3.35	0.0004	-8,375	-3.4	0.0004	-8,500	NO	NO	£20,000
9	Breeze et al (2017)	-0.56	0.0001	-5,600	-0.59	0.0001	-5,900	NO	NO	£20,000
10	Breeze et al (2017)	0	0.0001	0	-0.02	0.0001	-200	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£20,000
11	Breeze et al (2017)	-23.85	0.0007	-34,071	-23.42	0.0007	-33,457	NO	NO	£20,000
12	Breeze et al (2017)	-4.8	0.0003	-16,000	-4.91	0.0003	-16,367	NO	NO	£20,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
13	Breeze et al (2017)	-3.35	0.0004	-8,375	-3.37	0.0004	-8,425	NO	NO	£20,000
14	Breeze et al (2017)	-0.56	0.0001	-5,600	-0.57	0.0001	-5,700	NO	NO	£20,000
15	Breeze et al (2017)	0	0.0001	0	-0.01	0.0001	-100	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£20,000
16	Breeze et al (2017)	-23.85	0.0007	-34,071	-23.9	0.0007	-34,143	NO	NO	£20,000
17	Jendel et al. (2017)	373,896	1.88	198,881	262,396	1.88	139,572	NO	NO	SEKs 300,000
18	Jendel et al. (2017)	350,484	1.067	328,476	268,899	1.067	252,014	YES	NO	SEKs 300,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
19	Landstedt-Hallin et al. (2017)	-22,757	0.54	-42,143	-39,152	0.54	-72,504	NO	NO	Not determined
20	Landstedt-Hallin et al. (2017)	-22,757	0.92	-24,736	-39,152	0.92	-42,557	NO	NO	Not determined
21	Landstedt-Hallin et al. (2017)	-19,075	0.24	-79,479	-29,456	0.24	-122,733	NO	NO	Not determined
22	Landstedt-Hallin et al. (2017)	-34,606	0.81	-42,723	-48,892	0.81	-60,360	NO	NO	Not determined
23	Landstedt-Hallin et al. (2017)	-33,890	0.45	-75,311	-62,451	0.45	-138,780	NO	NO	Not determined
24	Roze et al. (2017)	305,638	1.45	210,785	226,023	1.45	155,878	NO	NO	DKK 225,000
25	Roze et al. (2017)	227,793	1.88	121,167	168,682	1.88	89,725	NO	NO	DKK 225,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
26	Slangen et al. (2017)	16,569	0.22	75,314	21,226	0.22	96,481	YES	NO	€80,000
27	Farshchi et al. (2016)	-136	0.08	-169	-171	0.08	-2,134	NO	NO	\$20,000
28	Haig et al. (2016)	9,849	0.4	24,494	-18,993	0.4	-47,483	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	CAN\$ 50,000
29	Haig et al. (2016)	11,471	0.32	36,414	-11,114	0.32	-34,731	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	CAN\$ 50,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
30	Kolu et al. (2016)	-221	0.24	-921	-1,300	0.24	-5,417	NO	NO	Not determined
31	Lian et al (2016)	598,537	1.25	478,830	249,676	1.25	199,741	NO	NO	Not determined
32	Lian et al (2016)	1,213,042	7.28	166,627	1,048,655	7.28	144,046	NO	NO	Not determined
33	Nguyen et al. (2016)	-144	0	-	-173	0	-	NO	NO	Singapore S\$ 63,000
34	Roussel et al (2016)	2,558	0.25	10,275	2,289	0.25	9,197	NO	NO	€30,000
35	Roussel et al (2016)	4,695	0.23	20,709	4,417	0.23	19,482	NO	NO	€30,000
36	Roze et al. (2016)	36,568	2.99	12,233	10,042	2.99	3,359	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
37	Roze et al. (2016)	35,801	1.187	30,163	31,884	1.187	26,863	YES	NO	€30,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
38	Roze et al. (2016)	27,051	0.43	62,909	26,010	0.43	60,488	NO	NO	€80,000
39	Brown et al. (2015)	56,366	0.9981	56,445	-30,807	0.9981	-30,866	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	\$50,000 – 100,000
40	Cutino et al (2015)	18,880	0.1288	146,584	5,015	0.1288	38,948	YES	NO	\$50000
41	Cutino et al (2015)	13,548	0.1288	105,186	-1,367	0.1288	-10,613	YES	NO	\$50000
42	Cutino et al (2015)	26,034	0.1288	202,127	11,119	0.1288	86,328	NO	NO	\$50000
43	Huetson et al (2015)	-7,469	0.066	-113,167	-6,869	0.066	-104,076	NO	NO	NOKs 500,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
44	Roze et al (2015)	415,106	0.76	545,005	279,962	0.76	367,571	YES	NO	SEKs 500,000
45	Kiadaliri (2014)	31,510	0.1	315,100	34,865	0.1	348,650	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
46	Kiadaliri (2014)	29,598	0.25	118,392	40,802	0.25	163,208	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
47	Kiadaliri (2014)	-1,912	0.15	-12,747	5,936	0.15	39,573	NO	YES, when social costs are included, the intervention is no longer cost-saving	SEKs 500,000
48	Png et al (2014)	846	0.05	17,184	1804	0.05	36,663	NO	NO	\$53,000
49	Png et al (2014)	846	0.05	17,184	1802	0.05	36,609	NO	NO	\$53,000
50	Png et al (2014)	846	0.05	17,184	1793	0.05	36,440	NO	NO	\$53,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
51	Png et al (2014)	281	0.01	21,065	-19,915	0.01	-1,991,500	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	\$53,000
52	Png et al (2014)	281	0.01	21,065	84	0.01	8,400	NO	NO	\$53,000
53	Png et al (2014)	281	0.01	21,065	79	0.01	7,900	NO	NO	\$53,000
54	Steen-Carlsson & Persson (2014)	56,805	0.36	157,792	80,358	0.36	223,217	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
55	Steen-Carlsson & Persson. (2014)	59,289	0.31	191,255	77,234	0.31	249,142	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
56	Steen-Carlsson & Persson. (2014)	56,855	0.36	157,931	82,452	0.36	229,033	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
57	Steen-Carlsson & Persson. (2014)	59,891	0.32	187,159	80,566	0.32	251,769	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
58	Steen-Carlsson & Persson. (2014)	37,512	0.38	98,716	56,624	0.38	149,011	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
59	Steen-Carlsson & Persson. (2014)	38,638	0.33	117,085	51,898	0.33	157,267	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
60	Steen-Carlsson & Persson. (2014)	37,267	0.38	98,071	57,603	0.38	151,587	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
61	Steen-Carlsson & Persson. (2014)	39,110	0.34	115,029	54,411	0.34	160,032	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
62	Tsiachristas (2014)	-677	0.013	-52077	-1735	0.013	-133462	NO	NO	Not determined
63	Ericsson (2013)	905	0.044	20,562	878	0.044	19,766	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
64	Ericsson (2013)	987	0.08	12,334	802	0.08	10,082	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
65	Ericsson (2013)	4,035	0.09	44,831	3,251	0.09	36,074	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
66	Saha (2013)	1,580	0.95	1,885	9,800	0.95	10,537	NO	NO	\$76,000
67	Salas-Cansado (2012)	174	0.101	14,381	151	0.101	5,302	NO	NO	€30,000
68	Kamble et al (2012)	86,324	0.376	229,675	79,678	0.376	211,991	NO	NO	\$100,000
69	Kamble et al (2012)	63,182	0.376	168,104	56,536	0.376	150,420	NO	NO	\$100,000
70	Oostdam (2012)	842	-0.005	-168,400	986	-0.005	-208,558	NO	NO	Not determined

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
71	Oostdam (2012)	842	-0.005	-168,400	1029	-0.005	-217,602	NO	NO	Not determined
72	Smith-Palmer (2012)	-5,677	0.11	-51,609	-23,217	0.11	-211,064	NO	NO	Not determined
73	Greeley et al. (2011)	-7,677	0.32	-23,991	-12,528	0.32	-39,150	NO	NO	\$200,000
74	Greeley et al. (2011)	-17,576	0.55	-31,956	-23,227	0.55	-42,231	NO	NO	\$200,000
75	Greeley et al. (2011)	-24,789	0.7	-35,413	-30,437	0.7	-43,481	NO	NO	\$200,000
76	Kasteng et al. (2011)	-13,221	0.08	-165,263	-10,079	0.08	-125,988	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
77	Kasteng et al. (2011)	-9,207	0.09	-102,300	-12,087	0.09	-134,300	NO	NO	SEKs 500,000
78	Kuo et al. (2011)	5,311	0.117	45,393	4,909	0.117	41,957	NO	NO	\$50,000-100,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
79	Patel et al. (2011)	340	0.011	30,909	449	0.011	40,818	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
80	Patel et al. (2011)	535	0.011	48,636	643	0.011	58,455	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
81	Patel et al. (2011)	127	0.003	42,333	149	0.003	49,667	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
82	Patel et al. (2011)	790	0.003	263,333	814	0.003	271,333	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
83	Patel et al. (2011)	-287	-0.008	35,875	-323	-0.008	40,375	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
84	Patel et al. (2011)	178	-0.008	-22,250	144	-0.008	-18,000	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
85	Patel et al. (2011)	340	0.004	85,000	449	0.004	112,250	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
86	Patel et al. (2011)	535	0.004	133,750	643	0.004	160,750	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
87	Patel et al. (2011)	127	0.0002	635,000	149	0.0002	745,000	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
88	Patel et al. (2011)	790	0.0002	3,950,000	814	0.0002	4,070,000	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
89	Patel et al. (2011)	-287	-0.004	71,750	-323	-0.004	80,750	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
90	Patel et al. (2011)	178	-0.004	-44,500	144	-0.004	-36,000	NO	NO	£20,000 – 30,000
91	Valentine et al. (2011)	1,023	0.15	6,820	-346	0.15	-2,307	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€40,000 – 60,000
92	Valentine et al. (2011)	26,144	0.53	49,328	-80,113	0.53	-151,157	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving	SEKs 100,000 – 400,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
									and, hence, dominates the comparator	
93	Huang et al. (2010)	58,134	0.6	96,890	58,767	0.6	97,945	NO	NO	\$50,000 – 100,000
94	Huang et al. (2010)	84,765	1.11	76,365	87,386	1.11	78,726	NO	NO	\$50,000 – 100,000
95	Ismail et al (2010)	458	0.007	65,429	550	0.007	78,571	NO	NO	£20,000
96	Ismail et al (2010)	707	-0.0001	-7,070,000	718	-0.0001	-7,180,000	NO	NO	£20,000
97	Ismail et al (2010)	226	-0.007	-32,286	182	-0.007	-26,000	NO	NO	£20,000
98	Ismail et al (2010)	458	0.002	229,000	550	0.002	275,000	NO	NO	£20,000
99	Ismail et al (2010)	707	0.0002	3,535,000	718	0.0002	3,590,000	NO	NO	£20,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
100	Ismail et al (2010)	226	-0.002	-91,000	182	-0.002	-91,000	NO	NO	£20,000
101	Gschwend (2009)	-854	0.47	-1,817	-10,545	0.47	-22,436	NO	NO	Not determined
102	Lindgren et al. (2007)	1,673	0.2	8,365	-1,853	0.2	-9,265	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	Not determined
103	Valentine et al. (2006)	10,451	0.698	14,973	5,763	0.698	8,256	NO	NO	\$50,000
104	Eddy et al. (2005)	22,737	0.159	143,000	9,969	0.159	62,698	YES	NO	\$100,000
105	Herman et al. (2005)	635	0.57	1,114	4,967	0.57	8,714	NO	NO	£20,000 – 100,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
106	Herman et al. (2005)	3,922	0.13	30,169	3,748	0.13	28,831	NO	NO	£20,000 – 100,000
107	Rosen et al. (2005)	-1,606	0.23	-6,983	-2,501	0.23	-10,874	NO	NO	\$20,000
108	The Diabetes Prevention Program Research Group (2003)	1,121	0.035	32,029	1,829	0.035	52,250	NO	NO	Not determined
109	The Diabetes Prevention Program Research Group (2003)	1,635	0.016	102,164	1,627	0.016	101,713	NO	NO	Not determined
110	Almbrand et al. (2000)	6,204	0.66	9,400	15,906	0.66	24,100	NO	NO	€60,000

A change in conclusions is identified when, in cases where social costs are included, the conclusion about the adoption of a new technology is modified (i.e. from the healthcare payer's perspective, the ICUR is above the threshold value and, hence, the assessed technology will not be implemented as it is not cost-effective. However, when social costs are included, the ICUR is modified so that it lies below the corresponding threshold and the technology will be implemented). A change in results is reported when, although the conclusions do not change, when social costs are introduced, the intervention might become cost-saving, as the incremental costs might switch from positive from the healthcare perspective to negative from the societal perspective.

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Appendix 3. RARE DISEASES

Figure 1: Flowchart of study identification and selection criteria

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Table 1: Characteristics of the studies included in the review.

Authors & year of publication	Disease	Intervention type	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included in the economic assessment	Method used for calculating the social costs
Sheng et al. (2017)	Chronic myeloid leukemia	Care delivery	3%; 3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : adverse event costs, outpatient visits, hospital stays, tests, transplantation, monitoring. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care costs	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach (paid time) <u>Informal care costs</u> : opportunity cost method
Landfeldt et al. (2017)	Duchenne Muscular dystrophy	Diagnostic	3.5%; 3.5%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : hospital admissions, visits to physicians and other healthcare professionals, medical tests and assessments, medications, emergency and respite care, costs associated with non-medical aids. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care costs	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism and presenteeism)) <u>Informal care costs</u> : opportunity cost method (paid and unpaid time)
Borg et al. (2016)	Multiple Myeloma	Pharmaceutical	3%; 3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : medication, laboratory tests, monitoring and adverse events. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach (paid time)
Park et al. (2016)	Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis	Pharmaceutical	5%; 5%	20 years	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : drug costs, clinical and laboratory tests, inpatient and outpatient care, surgery, end-of-life palliative care. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach (paid time)
Diel et al. (2015)	Tuberculosis	Pharmaceutical	3%; 3%	10 years	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : medications, monitoring, hospitalizations, secondary outpatient care. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism and premature mortality))
van Dussen et al. (2014)	Type 1 Gaucher disease	Pharmaceutical	4%; 1%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : inpatient hospital day, in-hospital day-care treatment, diagnostic tests, drugs, outpatient hospital care, GP, specialist consultations, social carer, alternative healer. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism and early retirement))

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Authors & year of publication	Disease	Intervention type	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included in the economic assessment	Method used for calculating the social costs
Kanters et al. (2014)	Pompe disease	Pharmaceutical	4%; 1.5%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : the cost of the drug alglucosidase alfa, infusion-related costs, costs related to other healthcare use. <u>Social costs</u> : informal care	<u>Informal care costs</u> : opportunity cost
Kulpeng et al. (2014)	Chronic Myeloid Leukemia	Pharmaceutical	3%; 3%	lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : aspolymerase-chain reaction testing, complete blood count, cytogenetic analysis, bone marrow aspiration, other laboratory tests, transport costs. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss</u> : n.a. (paid time (absenteeism))
Wilson et al. (2014)	Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis	Pharmaceutial	n.a.; n.a.	12 months	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : drugs, primary and secondary care, other healthcare professionals, social services, out-of-pocket expenditure. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach (paid time) <u>Informal care costs</u> : n.a. (paid time)
Rombach et al. (2013)	Fabry-Anderson disease	Pharmaceutial	0 and 4%; 0 and 1.5%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : inpatient hospital day, inpatient hospital intensive care unit day, in hospital day-care treatment, drugs, kidney treatment and transplantation, other diagnostic and therapeutic procedures, outpatient hospital visits, out-of-hospital visit. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism and early retirement))
Ghatnekar et al. (2010)	Chronic Myeloid Leukemia	Pharmaceutial	3%; 3%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : haematologist visit, inpatient stay, laboratory tests and diagnostic procedures, transfusion, drugs. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss</u> : human capital approach
Risebrough et al. (2008)	Haemophilia	Pharmaceutical	3%; 3%	5 years	<u>Healthcare cost</u> : costs of FVIII, laboratory tests, physician visits, clinic visits, nursing visits, physiotherapy, home treatment education, Port insertion, Port	<u>Informal care costs</u> : opportunity cost (paid time)

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Authors & year of publication	Disease	Intervention type	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included in the economic assessment	Method used for calculating the social costs
					complications and emergency room and hospital days for haemorrhagic events. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care costs	
Miners et al. (2002)	Haemophilia	Care delivery / Pharmaceutical	6%; 0%	Lifetime	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> costs of FVIII, outpatient and inpatient visits, physiotherapy, major surgery. <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss:</u> human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))
Gulbrandsen et al. (2001)	Multiple Myeloma	Pharmaceutical	5%; 0%	3 years	<u>Healthcare cost:</u> hospital days, visits to doctors and nurses, transfusions. <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity loss:</u> human capital approach (paid time (absenteeism))

GP= General Practitioner; FVIII= Protein Factor VIII; n.a= Not available

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Table 2: Results from full economic evaluations of rare diseases included in the review.

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
1	Sheng et al. (2017)	513,708	5.5	93,401	277,030	5.5	50,641	YES	NO	RMB74,000
2	Landfeldt et al. (2016)	1,520,450	1.05	1,442,710	1,492,900	1.05	1,266,510	NO	NO	£100,000
3	Landfeldt et al. (2016)	1,524,250	0.79	1,939,590	1,507,870	0.79	1,760,650	NO	NO	£100,000
4	Landfeldt et al. (2016)	1,524,520	0.43	3,574,770	1,519,040	0.43	3,121,890	NO	NO	£100,000
5	Park 2016	13,961,659	1.2	11,638,656	3,602,161	1.2	3,002,817	NO	NO	KRW26,000,000
6	Borg 2016	392,108	0.7351	533,382	-8,177	2.34	537,713	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	Not provided
7	Diel 2015	11,889.52	2.34	5,084	-8,177	2.34	-3,494	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving	€10,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
									and, hence, dominates the comparator	
8	Wilson 2014	50	0.032	1,567	-970	0.051	-19,020	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£20,000-30,000
9	Wilson 2014	365	0.053	6,818	1,177	0.053	22,012	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
10	Wilson 2014	44	0.045	993	-2,152	0.057	-37,754	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£20,000-30,000
11	Wilson 2014	287	0.059	4,849	674	0.059	11,400	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
12	van Dussen 2014	5,544,693	12.8	432,540	5,478,670	12.8	428,096	NO	NO	€10,000,000
13	van Dussen 2014	5,544,693	12.8	884,994	5,478,670	12.8	874,456	NO	NO	€10,000,000
14	Kulpeng 2014	-24,460,623	2.13	-1,151,235	-1,631,331	2.13	-765,883	NO	NO	THB 120,000
15	Kulpeng 2014	-26,941,323	2.57	11,115	-214,406	2.57	83,426	NO	NO	THB 120,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
16	Kanters 2014	6,843,318	6.75	1,013,825	7,000,028	6.75	1,043,868	NO	NO	€10,000,000
17	Rombach 2013	2,420,956	0.7	3,282,252	2,298,986	0.7	3,284,265	NO	NO	€20,000-100,000
18	Rombach 2013	9,647,388	1.6	6,065,529	9,716,810	1.6	6,073,006	NO	NO	€20,000-100,000
19	Ghatnekar 2010	4,452	0.62	7,181	4,250	0.62	6,855	NO	NO	€68,190
20	Risebrough 2008	193,144	0.3	643,813	165,976	0.3	553,253	NO	NO	\$1,000,000
21	Risebrough 2008	131,463	0.01	13,146,300	126,650	0.01	1,266,500	NO	NO	\$1,000,000
22	Miners 2002	694,070	11.79	58,869	687,910	11.79	58,347	NO	NO	£100,000
23	Miners 2002	694,070	3.34	207,805	687,910	3.34	205,961	NO	NO	£100,000
24	Miners 2002	133,818	11.79	11,350	127,658	11.79	10,828	NO	NO	£100,000
25	Miners 2002	133,818	3.34	40,065	127,658	3.34	38,221	NO	NO	£100,000
26	Gulbrandsen 2001	32,300	1.2	27,000	31,116	1.2	25,930	NO	NO	\$50,000-100,000

The threshold values were suggested by the authors in the text according to the local recommendations or suggestions. RMB: Renminbi; KRW: South Korean Won; THB: Thai Baht; £: Pounds Sterling; \$: US Dollars; €: Euros.

A change in conclusions is identified when, in cases where social costs are included, the conclusion about the adoption of a new technology is modified (i.e. from the healthcare payer's perspective, the ICUR is above the threshold value and, hence, the assessed technology will not be implemented as it is not cost-effective. However, when social costs are included, the ICUR is modified so

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that it lies below the corresponding threshold and the technology will be implemented). A change in results is reported when, although the conclusions do not change, when social costs are introduced, the intervention might become cost-saving, as the incremental costs might switch from positive from the healthcare perspective to negative from the societal perspective.

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Appendix 4. MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS

Figure 1. PRISMA flowchart of the search strategy

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Table 1. Descriptive information about the selected studies (n = 29)

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Ball et al. (2015)	Non-pharmacological treatment	United Kingdom (2010/2011£)	3.5%; 3.5%	3 years	Healthcare provider's perspective (societal perspective in a secondary analysis)	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : intervention and medication costs, hospital admissions, primary and acute care services, alternative practitioners, formal personal care services, home adaptations and equipment, day care, respite care, treatment-related travel. <u>Social costs</u> : informal care	<u>Informal care</u> : replacement cost method
Bell et al. (2007)	Care delivery / pharmaceutical	United States (2005\$)	3%; 3%	Lifetime	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective could be extracted from the tables)	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : drug acquisition costs, health state-related costs. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach
Bogosian et al. (2015)	Non-pharmacological treatment	United Kingdom (2012/2013£)	n.a.; n.a.	3 months	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective could be extracted from the text)	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : hospital (inpatient visits and hospitalizations) and community health and social care costs. <u>Social costs</u> : informal care	<u>Informal care</u> : n.a.
Caloyeras et al. (2012)	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2009 SEKs)	3%; 3%	Lifetime	Societal perspective (healthcare perspective could be extracted from tables)	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : inpatient and outpatient care, tests, medications, adverse event costs, services and investments.	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (early retirement and absenteeism)

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Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						<u>Social costs:</u> informal care and productivity losses	<u>Informal care:</u> n.a.
Chevalier et al. (2016)	Pharmaceutical	France (2013€)	4%; 4%	Lifetime	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> annual treatment acquisition, administration and monitoring costs, inpatient care, outpatient care, tests, prescription drugs other than DMTs, investments in additional resources for care, state costs and costs associated with relapses. <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (early retirement, temporary disability and absenteeism)
Earnshaw et al. (2009)	Pharmaceutical	United States (2007\$)	3%; 3%	Lifetime	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medical costs, non-medical costs (devices and investments to adapt living conditions). <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Frasco et al. (2017)	Care delivery / pharmaceutical	United States (2016\$)	3%; 3%	30 years	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective could be extracted from the tables)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient and outpatient admissions, office visits to physicians and other healthcare professionals, examinations, medications (non-DMT prescription drugs, over-the-counter medicines), medical devices, and alterations to the home and services.	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (early retirement, temporary disability and absenteeism) <u>Informal care:</u> opportunity cost

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						<u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	method (paid and unpaid time)
Furneri et al. (2019)	Pharmaceutical	Italy (2015€)	3.5%; 3.5%	50 years	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective could be extracted from the tables)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> cost of disability, treatment acquisition, administration, monitoring, relapses, adverse events-related costs <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach
Gani et al. (2008)	Pharmaceutical	United Kingdom (2006£)	3.5%; 3.5%	30 years	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective in the sensitivity analysis)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient admissions, nursing home care, day admissions, rehabilitation, healthcare specialists, diagnostic tests, non-DMT drug costs, home visits by nurses. <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a.
Gras & Broughton (2016)	Pharmaceutical	United Kingdom (2014£)	3.5%; 3.5%	30 years	Healthcare provider's perspective (societal perspective in a secondary analysis)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> community-based visits, outpatient clinic visits, A&E visits, hospital admission, home care visits, equipment costs. <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	<u>Informal care:</u> n.a.
Hettle et al. (2018)	Pharmaceutical	United Kingdom (2016£)	3.5%; 3.5%	50 years	Healthcare provider's perspective (societal perspective in a secondary analysis)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> drug acquisition, drug administration, and drug monitoring.	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. <u>Informal care:</u> n.a.

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Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						<u>Social costs</u> : informal care and productivity losses	
Imani & Golestani (2012)	Pharmaceutical	Iran (2011\$)	7.2%, 7.2%	Lifetime	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective could be extracted from the tables)	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : drug acquisition and health-state related costs. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach
Iskedjian et al. (2005)	Pharmaceutical	Canada (2001 CAN\$)	5%; 5%	15 years	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : medications, pharmacist visits, medication administration fees, physicians' fees, diagnostic procedures, laboratory testing fees, hospitalization costs. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (paid and unpaid time)
Jankovic et al. (2009)	Pharmaceutical	Serbia (2008 RSDs)	3%; 3%	40 years	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : drug acquisition costs and health-state related costs. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach
Kobelt et al. (2008)	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2005€)	3%; 3%	20 years	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : MS-related inpatient and outpatient care, rehabilitation, tests and drugs, walking aids and wheelchairs as well as nurse visits, home help and personal assistants, adaptation of their home or car.	<u>Productivity losses</u> : n.a. (absenteeism and early retirement) <u>Informal care</u> : n.a.

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Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						<u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	
Kobelt et al. (2000)	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (1998\$)	3%; 3%	10 years	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective in the sensitivity analysis)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> hospitalization, medical, and other visits (visits to physicians, nurses, and to rehabilitation centres as well as to paramedical practitioners), prescription and non-prescription drug usage, community and other services, adaptations of the home or the workplace, medical and other devices purchased. <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care cost	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism, temporary disability and early retirement) <u>Informal care:</u> n.a.
Kobelt et al. (2002)	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (2000\$)	3%; 3%	10 years	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective could be extracted from the tables)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> detection, treatment, rehabilitation, long-term care, and investments. <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism, temporary disability and early retirement) <u>Informal care:</u> n.a.
Kobelt et al. (2009)	Care delivery / medical procedure	France (2007€)	3%; 3%	10 & 20 years	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective could be extracted from the tables)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient care, outpatient care, tests, drugs, investments, home help services.	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism,

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Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						<u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	temporary disability and early retirement) <u>Informal care:</u> n.a.
Kobelt et al. (2003)	Pharmaceutical	Sweden (1999€)	3%; 3%	10 years	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> drug costs and health-state and relapse-related costs. <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care costs	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism, temporary disability and early retirement) <u>Informal care:</u> n.a.
Lazzaro et al. (2009)	Pharmaceutical	Italy (2006€)	3%; 3%	25 years	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> DMD and other drugs; outpatient diagnostic procedures, consultations and laboratory tests; hospitalization (inpatient and day-hospital); physical therapy; walking aids (such as canes, tripods, manual and electrical wheelchairs). <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism) <u>Informal care:</u> opportunity cost method (paid and unpaid time)
Mauskopf et al. (2016)	Pharmaceutical	United States (2015\$)	3%; 3%	20 years	Healthcare provider's perspective (societal perspective in a secondary analysis)	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> acquisition, administration, and monitoring costs and relapse-related costs.	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. <u>Informal care:</u> n.a.

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Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
						<u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care	
Mosweu et al. (2017)	Care delivery	United Kingdom (2009£)	n.a.; n.a.	1 year	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : medication, inpatient, out-patient appointments, laboratory tests and scans, emergency department, contact with community professionals. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach (absenteeism) <u>Informal care</u> : replacement cost method
Noyes et al. (2011)	Pharmaceutical	United States (2008\$)	3%; 3%	10 years	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective in the sensitivity analysis)	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : number of hospital admissions, outpatient treatments, emergency room visits, office visits, mental health visits, home health provider visits, home personal care use, and blood tests and MRI procedures. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses</u> : human capital approach <u>Informal care</u> : opportunity cost method
Nuijten & Hutton (2002)	Pharmaceutical	United Kingdom (1998£)	6%; n.a.	Lifetime	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<u>Healthcare costs</u> : relapse-related direct costs. <u>Social costs</u> : productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses</u> : friction cost method (paid time (absenteeism) and unpaid time)

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Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
							<u>Informal care:</u> replacement cost method
Pan et al. (2012)	Pharmaceutical	United States (2011\$)	3%; 3%	Lifetime	Societal perspective (healthcare provider's perspective could be extracted from the tables)	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> treatment costs, relapse-related direct costs, EDSS-specific direct disease management costs (inpatient care, outpatient care, tests, over-the-counter drugs and services).</p> <p><u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism, presenteeism, early retirement and premature mortality)</p> <p><u>Informal care:</u> n.a. (unpaid time)</p>
Soini et al. (2017)	Pharmaceutical	Finland (2014€)	3%; 3%	15 years	Healthcare provider's perspective (societal perspective in a secondary analysis)	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> drug, administration and monitoring costs, and adverse-event related costs.</p> <p><u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses</p>	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a.
Taheri et al. (2019)	Pharmaceutical	Iran (2018\$)	7.2%; 3%	20 years	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> drug acquisition costs, EDSS state-related costs, hospitalization, AEs, rehabilitation, transport, wheelchair, and investments to adapt modifications to home or car.</p> <p><u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses</p>	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (productivity losses due to morbidity and mortality)

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Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Perspective applied	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Tosh et al. (2014)	Health education or behaviour	United Kingdom (2011£)	n.a.; n.a.	9 months	Healthcare provider's perspective (societal perspective in a secondary analysis)	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> intervention costs (staff, equipment, overheads) and NHS costs (GP appointment, neurology outpatient visit, NHS community health visit, social care visit, neurology inpatient visit, hospitalisation, accident and emergency visit).</p> <p><u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)</p>
Touchette et al. (2003)	Pharmaceutical	United States (2000\$)	5%; 5%	10 years	Societal perspective and healthcare payer's perspective	<p><u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient and outpatient visits.</p> <p><u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care</p>	<p><u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a.</p> <p><u>Informal care:</u> n.a.</p>

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Table 2. Incremental costs, QALYs and ICURs from the healthcare payer/provider's and the societal perspectives

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
1	Ball et al (2015)	27,529	-0.0001	-275,290,000	30,294	-0.0001	-302,940,000	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
2	Bell et al (2007)	58,741	0.222	264,599	57,174	0.222	258,465	NO	NO	\$50,000
3	Bell et al (2007)	65,051	0.204	318,877	68,681	0.204	337,968	NO	NO	\$50,000
4	Bell et al (2007)	79,097	0.198	399,480	82,410	0.198	461,301	NO	NO	\$50,000
5	Bell et al (2007)	59,947	0.203	295,305	62,923	0.203	310,691	NO	NO	\$50,000
6	Bogosian et al (2015)	-720	0.01	-72,000	-2,285	0.01	-228,500	NO	NO	£20,000
7	Caloyeras et al (2012)	-167,000	0.479	-348,643	-344,000	0.479	-718,163	NO	NO	n.a.
8	Chevalier et al (2016)	-7,902	-0.281	28,121	-3,684	-0.281	13,110	NO	NO	€30,000-100,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
9	Chevalier et al (2016)	-4,649	-0.28	16,604	6	-0.28	-21	YES	NO	€30,000-100,000
10	Chevalier et al (2016)	-6,010	-0.452	13,296	10,301	-0.452	-22,790	YES	NO	€30,000-100,000
11	Chevalier et al (2016)	4,858	-0.321	-15,134	10,837	-0.321	-33,760	NO	NO	€30,000-100,000
12	Chevalier et al (2016)	-3,692	-0.224	16,482	849	-0.224	-3,790	YES	NO	€30,000-100,000
13	Chevalier et al (2016)	45,103	-0.25	-180,412	49,460	-0.25	-197,840	NO	NO	€30,000-100,000
14	Earnshaw et al (2009)	66,564	0.134	496,746	-56,322	0.134	-420,313	YES	NO	\$50,000
15	Earnshaw et al (2009)	80,772	0.133	607,308	-31,850	0.133	-239,474	YES	NO	\$50,000
16	Frasco et al (2017)	-255,498	0.84	-304,164	-287,713	0.84	-342,515	NO	NO	\$100,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
17	Furneri et al (2019)	62,850	1.52	41,349	-18,928	1.52	-12,453	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€50,000
18	Gani et al (2008)	35,530	1.9	18,700	4,300	1.9	2,263	NO	NO	£30,000
19	Gani et al (2008)	24,700	1.9	13,000	4,300	1.9	2,263	NO	NO	£30,000
20	Gras & Broughton (2016)	3,836	0.35	10,891	-33,609	0.35	95,423	NO	NO	£30,000
21	Hettle et al (2018)	-11,652	0.868	-13,424	-22,965	0.968	-23,724	NO	NO	£30,000
22	Hettle et al (2018)	-120,485	1.56	-77,234	-140,901	1.71	-82,398	NO	NO	£30,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
23	Imani & Golestani (2012)	125,101	0.204	613,240	123,909	0.204	607,397	NO	NO	\$50,000
24	Imani & Golestani (2012)	280,386	0.203	1,381,212	278,994	0.203	1,374,355	NO	NO	\$50,000
25	Imani & Golestani (2012)	2,323,420	0.198	11,734,444	230,970	0.198	1,166,515	NO	NO	\$50,000
26	Imani & Golestani (2012)	50,563	0.049	1,031,898	49,511	0.049	1,010,429	NO	NO	\$50,000
27	Iskedjian et al (2005)	65,000	0.2856	227,586	55,000	0.2856	189,286	NO	NO	\$50,000
28	Iskedjian et al (2005)	65,000	0.56	116,071	55,000	0.56	91,228	NO	NO	\$50,000
29	Jankovic et al (2009)	6,560,000	0.6	10,933,333	6,800,000	0.6	11,333,333	NO	NO	RSD5,000,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
30	Jankovic et al (2009)	16,960,000	0.6	28,266,667	16,700,000	0.6	27,833,333	NO	NO	RSD 5,000,000
31	Jankovic et al (2009)	16,960,000	0.6	28,266,667	16,600,000	0.6	27,666,667	NO	NO	RSD 5,000,000
32	Jankovic et al (2009)	15,060,000	0.6	25,100,000	14,800,000	0.6	24,666,667	NO	NO	RSD 5,000,000
33	Kobelt et al (2008)	13,010	0.34	38,145	-3,830	0.34	-11,265	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€50,000
34	Kobelt et al (2000)	102,800	0.162	634,600	55,500	0.162	342,700	NO	NO	\$30,000; 40,000; 100,000
35	Kobelt et al (2002)	9,700	0.217	44,700	5,577	0.217	25,700	YES	NO	\$30,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
36	Kobelt et al (2009)	10,800	0.15	72,000	2,250	0.15	15,000	YES	NO	€30,000
37	Kobelt et al (2009)	11,000	0.13	84,615	2,000	0.13	15,385	YES	NO	€30,000
38	Kobelt et al (2009)	13,400	0.15	89,333	10,700	0.15	71,333	NO	NO	€30,000
39	Kobelt et al (2009)	11,000	0.13	84,615	8,700	0.13	66,923	NO	NO	€30,000
40	Kobelt et al (2009)	15,500	0.07	221,429	11,250	0.07	160,714	NO	NO	€30,000
41	Kobelt et al (2009)	13,000	0.05	260,000	9,250	0.05	185,000	NO	NO	€30,000
42	Kobelt et al (2009)	16,000	0.07	228,571	15,000	0.07	214,286	NO	NO	€30,000
43	Kobelt et al (2009)	13,250	0.05	265,000	12,250	0.05	245,000	NO	NO	€30,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
44	Kobelt et al (2003)	9,562	0.192	49,800	1,500	0.192	7,800	NO	NO	€50,000
45	Lazzaro et al (2009)	894	0.35	2,575	-5,606	0.35	-16,018	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€5,500
46	Mauskopf et al (2016)	-33,059	0.359	-92,086	-39,896	0.359	-111,131	NO	NO	n.a.
47	Mauskopf et al (2016)	-33,059	0.359	-92,086	-48,834	0.359	-136,028	NO	NO	n.a.
48	Mosweu et al (2017)	1,610	0.0053	303,774	2,871	0.0053	541,698	NO	NO	£60,000
49	Noyes et al (2011)	198,747	0.192	1,035,140	173,053	0.192	901,319	NO	NO	n.a.

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
50	Noyes et al (2011)	218,535	0.173	1,263,207	194,307	0.173	1,123,162	NO	NO	n.a.
51	Noyes et al (2011)	191,039	0.082	2,329,739	178,642	0.082	2,178,555	NO	NO	n.a.
52	Noyes et al (2011)	20,6048	0.126	1,635,299	187,401	0.126	1,487,306	NO	NO	n.a.
53	Nuijten & Hutton (2002)	449,156	3.3	136,108	321,308	3.3	97,366	NO	NO	n.a.
54	Nuijten & Hutton (2002)	170,222	3.3	51,582	150,616	3.3	45,641	NO	NO	n.a.
55	Pan et al (2012)	113,784	5.1	22,311	175,610	5.1	34,433	NO	NO	\$50,000
56	Pan et al (2012)	36,789	1.9	19,363	86,223	1.9	45,381	NO	NO	\$50,000
57	Soini et al (2017)	16,077	0.477	33,704	2,000	0.477	4,193	NO	NO	€68,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
58	Soini et al (2017)	9,346	0.388	24,088	-2,000	0.388	-5,155	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€68,000
59	Soini et al (2017)	15,216	0.264	57,636	8,000	0.264	30,303	NO	NO	€68,000
60	Soini et al (2017)	35,876	0.144	249,139	33,000	0.144	229,167	NO	NO	€68,000
61	Soini et al (2017)	30,405	0.125	243,240	27,000	0.125	216,000	NO	NO	€68,000
62	Soini et al (2017)	75,362	-0.268	-281,201	85,000	-0.268	-317,164	NO	NO	€68,000
63	Taheri et al (2019)	-3,162	0.56	-5,646	-3,723	0.63	-5,910	NO	NO	n.a.

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
64	Tosh et al (2014)	466	0.046	10,137	1,144	0.046	24,897	NO	NO	£20,000-30,000
65	Tosh et al (2014)	466	0.024	19,783	1,144	0.024	47,667	YES	NO	£20,000-30,000
66	Touchette et al (2003)	7,047	0.121	58,240	-5,056	0.121	-41,785	YES	NO	\$50,000
67	Touchette et al (2003)	69,502	0.2052	338,704	50,412	0.2052	245,673	NO	NO	\$50,000

A change in conclusions is identified when, in cases where social costs are included, the conclusion about the adoption of a new technology is modified (i.e. from the healthcare payer's perspective, the ICUR is above the threshold value and, hence, the assessed technology will not be implemented as it is not cost-effective. However, when social costs are included, the ICUR is modified so that it lies below the corresponding threshold and the technology will be implemented). A change in results is reported when, although the conclusions do not change, when social costs are introduced, the intervention might become cost-saving, as the incremental costs might switch from positive from the healthcare perspective to negative from the societal perspective.

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Appendix 5. DEPRESSION

Figure 1: Flowchart of study identification and selection criteria

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Table 1. Summary of the main characteristics of the selected studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Annemans et al. (2014)	Pharmaceutical therapy	Belgium (2011€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> intervention costs, primary care <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and premature mortality)
Aragones et al. (2014)	Collaborative care	Spain (2011€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare, intervention <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Banerjee et al. (2013)	Pharmaceutical therapy	United Kingdom (2009£)	n.a./n.a.	13 weeks; 39 weeks	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medication, health and social care <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	<u>Informal care costs:</u> replacement cost method
Biesheuvel-Liefveld et al. (2018)	Prevention	The Netherlands (2013€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary & secondary care, mental healthcare, home care, medication, intervention <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and presenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> replacement cost method
Bosmans et al. (2008)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	The Netherlands (2002€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary & secondary care, non-healthcare, medication <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> n.a.

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Brettschneider et al. (2017)	Screening/diagnostic	Germany (2012€)	n.a./n.a.	6 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient & outpatient care, psychotherapist, medication, nursing care, informal care <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Buntrock et al. (2017)	Prevention	Germany (2013€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare use, out-of-pocket expenses <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism and presenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
Chalder et al. (2012)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	United Kingdom (2009£)	3.5%; n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary & secondary care, intervention, medication, patient & carers <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Choi et al. (2016)	Pharmaceutical therapy	South Korea (2014KRW)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> psychiatrist, AE, outpatient care, emergency, laboratory tests, medication <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism and premature mortality)
Dixon et al. (2016)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	United Kingdom (2012/13£)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary & secondary care, medication, inpatient, ambulance, intervention, personal social services, out-of-pocket expenses <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)
Ekman et al. (2012)	Pharmaceutical therapy	United Kingdom (2011£)	3.5%; 3.5%	5 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient and outpatient, medication <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Evans-Lacko et al. (2016)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	Germany (2013€)	3.5%; n.a.	27 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> screening, GP visits, primary care, inpatient, psychotherapist <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism and presenteeism)
Eveleigh et al. (2014)	Pharmaceutical therapy	The Netherlands (2012€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> health services & resources, intervention <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism)
Fernandez et al. (2018)	Prevention	Spain (2012€)	3.5%; n.a.	1.5 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medication, intervention <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism and presenteeism)
Gensichen et al. (2013)	Collaborative care	Germany (2006€)	n.a./n.a.	2 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> psychiatric inpatient care, outpatient psychological care, psychiatrists & GP visits, medication <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Gerhards et al. (2010)	Deterministic and probabilistic	The Netherlands (2007€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare use, costs for patient & family <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and presenteeism)
Goorden et al. (2015)	Collaborative care	The Netherlands (2013€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare use <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and presenteeism)
Goorden et al. (2014)	Collaborative care	The Netherlands (2009€)	n.a./n.a.	13 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare use <u>Productivity costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and presenteeism)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Green et al. (2014)	Collaborative care	United Kingdom (2011£)	n.a. / n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> intervention, health & social care service, supervision, specialists <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses, informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
Groessler et al. (2018)	Screening/diagnostic	United States (2016\$)	3%; n.a.	3 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medical services, intervention <u>Productivity costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)
Hollinghurst et al. (2014)	Combined intervention	United Kingdom (2010£)	n.a. / n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> health & social care services, intervention, out-of-pocket <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Hollinghurst et al. (2010)	Deterministic and probabilistic	United Kingdom (2007£)	n.a. / n.a.	8 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary and community contacts, mental health-related secondary care, social services, out-of-pocket expenses <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Hornberger et al. (2015)	Screening/diagnostic	United States (2013\$)	3%; n.a.	patient's lifetime	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medication, inpatient & outpatient, psychotherapy, intervention <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)
Joling et al. (2013)	Collaborative care	The Netherlands (2009€)	n.a. / n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> outpatient care, home care & other support, day hospital, inpatient <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses, informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Kessler et al. (2018)	Combined intervention	United Kingdom (2016£)	n.a. /n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient & outpatient care, private counselling, prescription charges, over-the-counter medication, complementary therapies, private home care <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Kolovos et al. (2016)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	The Netherlands (2013€)	n.a. /n.a.	13 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare & non-healthcare, <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses, informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and presenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> replacement cost method
Kuyken et al. (2015)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	United Kingdom (2011/12£)	3.5%; 3.5%	2 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary & secondary care, medication, social care & voluntary sector services, intervention, out-of-pocket expenses <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and presenteeism)
Maniadakis et al. (2013)	Pharmaceutical therapy	Greece (2012€)	3.5%; n.a.	2 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient care, outpatient visits, medication, laboratory tests, AE <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)
Meuldijk et al. (2015)	Combined intervention	The Netherlands (2013€)	n.a. /n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary care, non-healthcare use <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and presenteeism)
Nordstrom et al. (2012)	Pharmaceutical therapy	Sweden (2009€)	n.a. /n.a.	6 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> hospitalization, outpatient care, medication <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Nordstrom et al. (2010)	Pharmaceutical therapy	Sweden (2009€)	n.a./n.a.	6 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient & outpatient care, medication <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)
Nuijten et al. (2012)	Pharmaceutical therapy	The Netherlands (2010€)	n.a./n.a.	26 weeks	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient care, consultations, medication <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism)
Patel et al. (2017)	Combined intervention	India (2015\$)	n.a./n.a.	3 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> outpatient, inpatient, medication, intervention, laboratory tests <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses, informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> n.a.
Ramsberg et al. (2012)	Pharmaceutical therapy	Sweden (2009€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medication, primary care, specialist care <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)
Richards et al. (2016)	Collaborative care	United Kingdom (2011£)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary, secondary & community care, social care, out-of-pocket expenses <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	<u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
Richards et al. (2017)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	United Kingdom (2013/14£)	3.5%; 3.5%	1.5 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> hospital services, primary care, social service, complementary services, medications <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Romeo et al. (2013)	Pharmaceutical therapy	United Kingdom (2009/10£)	n.a./n.a.	39 weeks	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient, day hospital, outpatient, social care, occupational therapy, emergency <u>Social costs:</u> informal care	<u>Informal care costs:</u> replacement cost method (paid time only)
Romero-Sanchiz et al. (2017)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	Spain (2014€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medications, medical tests, use of health-related services <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Rubio-Valera et al. (2013)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	Spain (2009€)	n.a./n.a.	6 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> publicly & privately funded primary & secondary care, tests, hospitalisation, medications <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Sado et al. (2009)	Combined intervention	Japan (2005JPYs)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medications, consultant & psychotherapy fees, inpatient <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)
Serrano-Blanco et al. (2009)	Pharmaceutical therapy	Spain (2001€)	n.a./n.a.	6 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medications, GP visits, specialized medical visits, emergency, inpatient <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Simons et al. (2017)	Combined intervention	The Netherlands (2012€)	n.a./n.a.	32 weeks	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare use, medications, intervention <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism and presenteeism)
Simpson et al. (2009)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	United States (2006\$)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient, GP visits, emergency, medications	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
					<u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses, informal care	<u>Informal care costs:</u> n.a.
Snedecor et al. (2010)	Pharmaceutical therapy	United States (2007\$)	n.a./n.a.	2 months/ 6 months	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medication, medical & health services <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> n.a. (absenteeism and presenteeism)
Soini et al. (2017)	Pharmaceutical therapy	Finland (2014€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> psychiatrist & GP visits, psychotherapist, hospitalisations, medications <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Stant et al. (2009)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	The Netherlands (2003€)	3% and 5%; n.a.	3 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient & community care, healthcare, medications, intervention, non-medical <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses, informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> n.a.
van der Aa et al. (2017)	Collaborative care	The Netherlands (2013€)	n.a./n.a.	2 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> primary & secondary care, medications, intervention <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses, informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> friction cost method (absenteeism and presenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> opportunity cost method
van Eeden et al. (2015)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	The Netherlands (2012€)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> care provider utilization, complementary care, home care, medications, intervention, patient & family <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses, informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> replacement cost method
Vasiliadis et al. (2017)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	Canada (n.a. CAN\$)	n.a./n.a.	40 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medical and non-medical <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Authors & year of publication	Intervention type	Country and currency	Discount rate (Costs/ Outcomes)	Time horizon	Costs included	Method used for calculating social costs
Vataire et al. (2014)	Combined intervention	United Kingdom (2011£)	3.5%; 3.5%	5 years	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> inpatient, AE, GP & psychiatrist visits, medication, <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism and premature mortality)
Warmerdam et al. (2010)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	The Netherlands (2007€)	n.a./n.a.	12 weeks	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> medical & non-medical, intervention, out-of-pocket expenses, family & patients <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses and informal care	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism) <u>Informal care costs:</u> replacement cost method
Weobong et al. (2017)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	India (2015\$)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare use <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)
Wiles et al. (2014)	Non-pharmaceutical intervention	United Kingdom (2010£)	n.a./n.a.	1 year	<u>Healthcare costs:</u> healthcare use, intervention, social services <u>Social costs:</u> productivity losses	<u>Productivity losses:</u> human capital approach (absenteeism)

n.a.: not applicable/not available

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Table 2. Summary of the economic results of the selected studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		Δ Costs	Δ QALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Δ Costs	Δ QALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
1	Annemans et al. (2014)	16	0.003	6,352	-258	0.003	-86,000	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€30,000
2	Annemans et al. (2014)	-5	0.004	-1,250	-387	0.004	-96,750	NO	NO	€30,000
3	Annemans et al. (2014)	-37	0.008	-4,625	-829	0.008	-103,625	NO	NO	€30,000
4	Annemans et al. (2014)	-50	0.009	-5,556	-902	0.009	-100,222	NO	NO	€30,000
5	Annemans et al. (2014)	-104	0.016	-6,500	-1,618	0.016	-101,125	NO	NO	€30,000
6	Annemans et al. (2014)	-128	0.015	-8,533	-1,591	0.015	-106,067	NO	NO	€30,000

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Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
7	Annemans et al. (2014)	-118	0.006	-19,667	-843	0.006	-140,500	NO	NO	€30,000
8	Aragones et al. (2014)	183	0.045	4,056	157	0.045	3,499	NO	NO	€30,000
9	Banerjee et al. (2013)	693	0.03	23,100	705	0.03	23,500	NO	NO	£30,000
10	Banerjee et al. (2013)	404	0.05	8,080	-1,106	0.05	-22,120	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£30,000
11	Banerjee et al. (2013)	-289	0.02	-14,450	-1,811	0.02	-90,550	NO	NO	£30,000
12	Biesheuvel-Leliefeld et al. (2018)	1,107	0.03	33,025	2,114	0.03	63,051	NO	NO	€30,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
13	Bosmans et al. (2008)	181	-0.00045	-353,333	-751	-0.00045	1,668,889	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	NA
14	Brettschneider et al. (2017)	-1,031	0.0067	-153,881	-1,309	0.0067	-195,373	NO	NO	€50,000
15	Buntrock et al. (2017)	135	0.01	13,500	134	0.01	13,400	NO	NO	€20,000
16	Chalder et al. (2012)	296	0.014	20,834	1,813	0.014	129,500	YES	NO	£30,000
17	Choi et al. (2016)	-50,130	0.0131	-3,826,718	-623,229	0.0131	-47,574,733	NO	NO	NA
18	Dixon et al. (2016)	177	0.031	5,710	324	0.031	10,452	NO	NO	£30,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
19	Ekman et al. (2012)	323	0.038	8,591	485	0.043	11,173	NO	NO	£30,000
20	Evans-Lacko et al. (2016)	1,280	0.05	25,600	2,107	0.05	42,140	NO	NO	€50,000
21	Eveleigh et al. (2014)	-57	-0.02	2,850	-1,631	-0.02	70,180	NO	NO	€80,000
22	Eveleigh et al. (2014)	-97	-0.03	3,233	1,088	-0.03	-36,267	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention is no longer cost-saving	€80,000
23	Fernandez et al. (2018)	24	0.02	1,194	-16	0.02	-819	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€30,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
24	Gensichen et al. (2013)	989	0.02	38,429	-1,322	0.02	-66,092	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	NA
25	Gerhards et al. (2010)	-484	-0.01	48,400	-1,787	-0.01	178,700	NO	NO	€80,000
26	Gerhards et al. (2010)	-83	-0.01	8,300	-451	-0.01	45,100	NO	NO	€80,000
27	Goorden et al. (2015)	1,173	0.02	53,717	-1,131	0.02	-56,550	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€80,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
28	Goorden et al. (2014)	-709	-0.05	14,589	-2,226	-0.05	44,520	NO	NO	€80,000
29	Green et al. (2014)	271	0.019	14,248	-313	0.019	-16,465	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£30,000
30	Green et al. (2014)	316	0.051	6,198	-1,246	0.051	-24,434	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£30,000
31	Groessler et al. (2018)	-2,918	0.10	-29,180	-2,598	0.10	-25,980	NO	NO	\$50,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
32	Groessl et al. (2018)	-6,087	0.17	-35,806	-5,810	0.17	-34,176	NO	NO	\$50,000
33	Hollingshurst et al. (2014)	851	0.057	14,911	1,039	0.057	18,228	NO	NO	£30,000
34	Hollingshurst et al. (2010)	-25	0.034	-17,173	-330	0.034	-9,706	NO	NO	£30,000
35	Hornberger et al. (2015)	-3,711	0.316	-11,744	-3,764	0.316	-11,911	NO	NO	\$50,000
36	Joling et al. (2013)	75	0.04	1,875	4,149	0.04	157,534	YES	NO	€30,000
37	Joling et al. (2013)	187	0.006	31,167	2,631	0.006	438,299	NO	NO	€30,000
38	Kessler et al. (2018)	69	0.00935	7,380	463	0.00935	49,572	YES	NO	£20,000
39	Kolovos et al. (2016)	-38	0.01	-3,800	1,579	0.01	157,900	YES	NO	€30,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
40	Kuyken et al. (2015)	124	-0.04	-3,103	449	-0.04	-11,229	NO	NO	NA
41	Maniadakis et al. (2013)	350	0.026	13,682	14	0.026	547	NO	NO	€50,000
42	Maniadakis et al. (2013)	269	0.034	7,959	-215	0.034	-6,324	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€50,000
43	Maniadakis et al. (2013)	154	0.015	10,591	-28	0.015	-1,867	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€50,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
44	Maniadakis et al. (2013)	273	0.03	9,183	-129	0.03	-4,300	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€50,000
45	Meuldijk et al. (2015)	1,880	0.005	376,000	4,795	0.005	959,000	NO	NO	€33,600
46	Nordstrom et al. (2012)	-16	0.00865	-1,831	-169	0.00865	-19,555	NO	NO	€33,600
47	Nordstrom et al. (2010)	-41	0.025	-1,647	-507	0.025	-20,264	NO	NO	€33,600
48	Nordstrom et al. (2010)	-17	0.025	-687	-483	0.025	-19,308	NO	NO	€33,600
49	Nuijten et al. (2012)	103	0.0062	16,363	-263	0.0062	-42,419	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention	€80,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
									becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	
50	Nuijten et al. (2012)	126	0.0166	7,553	-1,992	0.0166	-120,000	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	€80,000
51	Patel et al. (2017)	46	0.005	9,333	5	0.005	957	NO	NO	NA
52	Ramsberg et al. (2012)	14	0.0036	3,732	-123	0.0036	-34,167	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	NA

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
53	Ramsberg et al. (2012)	-159	0.0045	-35,333	-327	0.0045	-72,667	NO	NO	NA
54	Ramsberg et al. (2012)	-11	0.0052	-2,115	-206	0.0052	-39,615	NO	NO	NA
55	Ramsberg et al. (2012)	-55	0.0072	-7,639	-325	0.0072	-45,139	NO	NO	NA
56	Ramsberg et al. (2012)	-79	0.0086	-9,186	-404	0.0086	-46,977	NO	NO	NA
57	Ramsberg et al. (2012)	-147	0.0117	-12,564	-588	0.0117	-50,256	NO	NO	NA
58	Ramsberg et al. (2012)	-179	0.0131	-13,664	-673	0.0131	-51,374	NO	NO	NA
59	Richards et al. (2016)	271	0.019	14,248	-313	0.019	-16,465	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence,	£20,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
									dominates the comparator	
60	Richards et al. (2017)	-343	0.05	-6,865	-2,070	0.05	-41,392	NO	NO	£30,000
61	Romeo et al. (2013)	693	0.03	23,100	705	0.03	23,500	NO	NO	£30,000
62	Romeo et al. (2013)	404	0.05	8,080	-1,106	0.05	-22,120	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention becomes cost-saving and, hence, dominates the comparator	£30,000
63	Romeo et al. (2013)	-289	0.02	-14,450	-1,811	0.02	-90,550	NO	NO	£30,000
64	Romero-Sanchiz et al. (2017)	-632	0.0567	-11,153	-644	0.0567	-11,390	NO	NO	€25,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
65	Romero-Sanchiz et al. (2017)	-466	0.0751	-6,204	-479	0.0751	-6,381	NO	NO	€25,000
66	Romero-Sanchiz et al. (2017)	-322	0.0793	-4,060	-409	0.0793	-5,160	NO	NO	€25,000
67	Romero-Sanchiz et al. (2017)	-295	0.0824	-3,576	41	0.0824	497	NO	YES, when social costs are introduced, the new intervention is no longer cost-saving	€25,000
68	Rubio-Valera et al. (2013)	962	0.01	3,592	1,866	0.01	9,872	NO	NO	€30,000
69	Sado et al. (2009)	27,411	0.08	342,638	-693,858	0.08	-8,673,225	YES	NO	JPYs 30,000
70	Sado et al. (2009)	27,411	0.03	913,700	-693,858	0.03	-23,128,600	YES	NO	JPYs 30,000

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
71	Serrano-Blanco et al. (2009)	71	-0.06	-1,180	639	-0.06	-10,643	NO	NO	NA
72	Simons et al. (2017)	423	0.07	6,043	1,141	0.07	16,300	NO	NO	€80,000
73	Simons et al. (2017)	1,052	0.13	8,092	1,741	0.13	13,392	NO	NO	€80,000
74	Simpson et al. (2009)	NA	NA	34,999	NA	NA	6,667	NO	NO	\$50,000
75	Simpson et al. (2009)	NA	NA	-1,123	NA	NA	-7,621	NO	NO	\$50,000
76	Snedecor et al. (2010)	174	0.0058	30,000	81	0.0058	13,881	NO	NO	\$50,000
77	Soini et al. (2017)	-223	0.0134	-16,642	-1,074	0.0134	-80,149	NO	NO	NA
78	Soini et al. (2017)	-128	0.0166	-7,711	-957	0.0166	-57,651	NO	NO	NA

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
79	Soini et al. (2017)	-110	0.025	-4,400	-720	0.025	-28,800	NO	NO	NA
80	Soini et al. (2017)	-238	0.0276	-8,623	-1,390	0.0276	-50,362	NO	NO	NA
81	Stant et al. (2009)	653	-0.21	-3,110	1,616	-0.21	-7,695	NO	NO	NA
82	Stant et al. (2009)	1,231	-0.16	-7,694	1,644	-0.16	-10,275	NO	NO	NA
83	Stant et al. (2009)	713	-0.04	-17,825	1,054	-0.04	-26,350	NO	NO	NA
84	van der Aa et al. (2017)	-1,154	0.03	-38,467	-877	0.03	-29,233	NO	NO	€30,000
85	van Eeden et al. (2015)	1281	0.01	107,455	-1,913	0.01	-160,390	YES	NO	€40,000
86	Vasiliadis et al. (2017)	-1,604	0.17	-9,435	-2,590	0.17	-15,235	NO	NO	NA

How relevant is the societal perspective in economic evaluations? Evidence from five case studies

Estimate number	Authors & publication year	Healthcare payer/provider's perspective			Societal perspective			Comparison of perspectives		Threshold value
		ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	ΔCosts	ΔQALYs	ICUR (Cost/QALY)	Do the conclusions change? (YES/NO)	Do the results change? (YES/NO)	
87	Vasiliadis et al. (2017)	-1,604	0.17	-9,435	-1,904	0.17	-11,200	NO	NO	NA
88	Vataire et al. (2014)	-243	0.078	-3,115	-1,400	0.078	-17,949	NO	NO	£30,000
89	Warmerdam et al. (2010)	455	0.01	45,500	256	0.01	22,609	YES	NO	€30,000
90	Warmerdam et al. (2010)	405	0.01	40,500	147	0.01	11,523	YES	NO	€30,000
91	Weobong et al. (2017)	-18	0.011	-1,721	-155	0.011	-14,438	NO	NO	\$16,060
92	Wiles et al. (2014)	850	0.057	14,911	814	0.053	15,358	NO	NO	£30,000

NA: Not available

A change in conclusions is identified when, in cases where social costs are included, the conclusion about the adoption of a new technology is modified (i.e. from the healthcare payer's perspective, the ICUR is above the threshold value and, hence, the assessed technology will not be implemented as it is not cost-effective. However, when social costs are included, the ICUR is modified so that it lies below the corresponding threshold and the technology will be implemented). A change in results is reported when, although the conclusions do not change, when social costs are introduced, the intervention might become cost-saving, as the incremental costs might switch from positive from the healthcare perspective to negative from the societal perspective.

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